

When Time Gets Rough: Understanding the Leadership Difficulty Experiences of Student Leaders in the New Normal

An Undergraduate Thesis
Presented to the Faculty of College of Teacher Education
Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Marbel Inc.
Koronadal City

In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the degree
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English

ROGEN I. LAUDE

May 2023

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

APPROVAL SHEET

This undergraduate research entitled “**WHEN TIME GETS ROUGH: UNDERSTANDING THE LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTY EXPERIENCES OF STUDENT LEADERS IN THE NEW NORMAL**” prepared and submitted by **Rogen I. Laude** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English, has been examined, and is hereby endorse for acceptance and approval.

ALBERT P. BALONGOY, PhD.
Adviser

PANEL OF EXAMINERS

Approved by the Committee on Oral Examination. _____.

REV. NOE GARCIA, PhD, RGC
Chairman

ROSE USERO, MAEd
Member

ARVILLE SETANOS, MAEd
Member

Accepted and approved in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Arts in Sociology.

JOHNNY S. BANTULO, EdD
Program Director

Date

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper is a product of hard work, money, and time. With grateful hearts, the researcher wanted to acknowledge the personalities involved in the completion of this research paper. The researcher would like to express her sincerest gratitude and appreciation to the following person who unselfishly gave their assistance in the realization of this study.

To the Vice President of the school and Research Adviser, **Albert P. Balongoy, Ph.D.** the researcher owed gratefulness for the learnings and spent time and effort for the success of the paper. For the patience and understanding and for the encouragement and moral support for the researcher's best outcome.

To **Arville V. Setanos, Dr. Noe Garcia, and Rose Usero**, the expert validators and panel of research, for the time and effort in checking and correcting the progress of the study.

To **Conses Dianne P. Fajartin, MAEd & Johnny S. Bantulo, EdD**, Program Director of the College of Teacher Education, for supporting and authorizing the researcher to conduct a survey.

To **Sir Ryan Garcia** who allowed his student leaders to be chosen as participants in this study.

To the **Participants** of the study, the researcher is grateful for the permission to disclose their life experiences, their cooperation, and honest responses that made the study possible.

To the parents of the researcher, **Mrs. Remia I. Laude** and **Mr. Romeo C. Laude** for the unconditional moral and financial support for the completion of the study.

To **Julius Flores** who helped the researcher with kindness and patience for the successful establishment of the study.

To his **Qualitative Researcher Classmates** who helped the researcher with kindness and patience for the successful establishment of the study.

Lastly, the researcher wants to thank the **Almighty God** for giving the strength, courage guidance, and everything need to make this research study successful.

ROGEN I. LAUDE

ABSTRACT

The descriptive qualitative method was used in this study to explore and understand the student leader's experiences during the new normal. The pieces of evidence gathered were conducted in February this year, from Banga National High School. The results of the study revealed the experiences of the student leaders which brought a huge impact and success on the study. The result of the study revealed that there are a lot of difficulties that student leaders are facing, such as disinterest and apathy, communication barriers, financial inadequacy, the inadequacy of budget for the organization, pandemic-related obstacles, hurdles in implementation and service delivery, a pile-load of tasks and parental prohibitions. That is why participants found ways to overcome such challenges by staying connected, maximizing alternatives, reaching out to others, looking into positivity, taking a breather, wearing another's shoes, and following the courtesy call. As evidenced by the participants' comments, they all face challenges, but they also have coping mechanisms in place to overcome them. Struggles may appear to be a roadblock to achieving their goals, but they are not a reason to give up; rather, they are an invitation to fight even in the most difficult circumstances. This study will help the recipient to understand more and to have a clearer vision of this kind of situation as explored and studied by the researcher. Thus, Student Leadership has an impact on student's perseverance, which is an important aspect of completing their leadership journey.

Keywords: Student leader, leadership difficulties, leadership journey, new normal, Philippines.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Content	Page
Title Page	664
Approval Sheet	665
Acknowledgement	666
Abstract	667
Table of Contents	668
List of Tables	670
List of Figures	670
Dedication	671
CHAPTER	
I INTRODUCTION	672
Rationale	672
Research Questions	672
Theoretical Lens	672
Significance of the Study	673
Delimitations and Limitations	673
Definition of Terms	674
Organization of the Study	674
II REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES	676
III METHODOLOGY	680
Research Design	680
Role of Researcher	680
Research Participants	680
Locale of the Study	680
Research Instruments	682
Data Collection	682
Analysis of Data	683
Trustworthiness	683
Ethical Consideration	684
IV RESULT AND DISCUSSION	685
Categorization of Data	685
Q1	685
Q2	691
Q3	694
V DISCUSSION	
Result 1	699
Result 2	699
Result 3	699
Implication for Practice	700
Implication for Future Research	700
Concluding Remarks	701

INTERVIEW MATRIX	703
REFERENCES	710
APPENDICES	713
A. Cover Letter	713
B. Informed Consent Form	714
C. Participant's Agreement Form	715
D. Interview Guide	716
E. Transcription of Data	717
F. Request Letter to the Validator	721
G. Validation Sheets for Interview Guide	722
H. Student Leader Adviser Consent Form	723
I. Parents' Consent Form	724
J. (Plagiarism Checker) Result	725

LIST OF TABLES

Table	Page
1.	Difficulties encountered during their leadership journey685
2.	Ways undertook to overcome those difficulties691
3.	Personal development gained in overcoming those difficulties 694

LIST OF FIGURES

Figures		Page
1.	Map of Banga National High School	681

DEDICATION

This research study is wholeheartedly dedicated to the Almighty God, for showering a blessing of knowledge and intelligence to the researcher, to finish this study, and also serve as an offering for all his greatness all the time.

To the beloved research adviser, the researcher dedicates this study to him for sacrificing his time to finish this study on time.

To our beloved friends, classmates from different programs, and outsider friends, the researcher dedicates this to them in giving moral support in times of need, downtrodden.

Lastly, the researcher gives and offers this to his loving family who supported him every step of the way, in terms of financial matters, and moral support which made this study possible for him to conduct and finish this study.

“To God Be All the Glory!”

ROGEN I. LAUDE

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

A. Rationale

Most educational institutions aim to prepare future leaders, enabling the students to advocate for their needs and the needs of others. The students have been given an equal opportunity to lead and perform different tasks to contribute something to the school. Most educational institutions mold and harness the students' potential abilities to lead and prepare them for their future endeavors. In addition, the importance of this study was to address the difficulties of the student leaders based on their experiences and point of view.

Before the pandemic, the authority and presence of the student leaders were needed to impose peace and order in school events and to facilitate and take the initiative. However, we are now in a new average education where all activities are conducted virtually, and the role and function of student leaders are vastly fading. Furthermore, school leaders play a crucial role in facilitating agreement on what 'building back better' or the 'new normal' should look like, ensuring that it is centered on the needs of students (Mutch, 2014).

Considering the situation that we are having right now, rising mental health issues, limited social interaction, and academic burnout are the most common difficulties that most students are dealing with nowadays. Through the difficulties mentioned above, student leaders should take action on these alarming issues. In addition, according to Griffiths et al. (2020), influential leaders work with their staff so that the school understands what trauma is and how to recognize possible signs of it. This should be the key to continual well-being and supporting others through a crisis. Resources on managing well-being through uncertainty and trauma-informed practice in schools are essential.

Furthermore, this study focused on the qualitative experience of the student leaders in facing the new normal with this endeavor; the participants' accounts were presented to the office, which supported and evaluated the student leaders' experience in this new normal. The qualitative methodology allows the researcher to expose the actual experiences of the participants in this study by identifying and interpreting the given data. The goal of this paper is to know and understand the student leader's experiences throughout their leadership journey based on the time of the new normal. This study was conducted in the specific time frame of the academic year 2021-2022 to provide facts and unbiased results.

B. Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- What are the difficulties encountered by student leaders during their leadership journey?
- In what ways do the student leaders undertake to overcome their leadership difficulties?
- What were the personal developments gained by the student leaders in overcoming their leadership difficulties?

C. Theoretical Lens

This part presents the explanation of variables, concepts, and theories related to the study.

Leadership is a skill that student leaders should have; you can have the knowledge and skills to facilitate and guide the people, and the act of service should be possessed. However, there were various difficulties along the way in experiencing good governance.

Supported by the theory of Fiedler (2013), a scientist who studied the personality and characteristics of leaders. In his theory, he states that there was no one best leadership style. Instead, a leader's effectiveness was based on the situation. Furthermore, Fiedler's contingency theory of leadership effectiveness was based on the studies of a wide range of group effectiveness, concentrated on the relationship between leadership and organizational performance.

This was one of the earliest situational-contingency leadership theories given by Fiedler. According to him, if an organization attempts to achieve group effectiveness through leadership, then there is a need for an underlying trait, assessing the situation faced by the leader and constructing a proper match between the two.

D. Significance of the Study

The study aimed to determine the difficulties they encounter during their leadership journey, the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties, and what personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties.

The result of the study would help and benefit school administrators, student leader advisers, student leaders, parents, researchers, and future researchers.

- **School Administrators.** This study would give valuable insights into understanding the context of the student leaders in the school in facing the new normal. Moreover, the result of this study would serve as their guide in planning efficient and effective programs for student leaders. This study would also serve as their guide in order for them to create a suitable environment for the student leaders to perform their duties and responsibilities.
- **Student Leader Advisers.** This study would provide valuable and significant information about the experiences of student leaders in facing the new normal. Moreover, they would realize the needs of the student leaders during their leadership journey. This would help them develop a more effective and efficient way of advising the student leaders, especially when they encounter difficulties in their leadership journey.
- **Student Leaders.** This study would make the student leaders appreciate and understand their roles as student leaders in facing the new normal. Moreover, this would help them create different ways to overcome the new standard's difficulties. This would help them analyze their roles and generate effective ways, especially when they face difficulties in their leadership journey.
- **Parents.** This study would help parents appreciate and understand their children's roles as student leaders in facing the new normal. Moreover, they would realize their roles in guiding their children, most especially when they face difficulty in their leadership journey. This would help them guide and motivate their children, especially in their challenging times as they encounter their leadership journey.
- **Researcher.** This study would assist the researcher in broadening his horizons by providing information and skills in dealing with various difficulties. This study would be a learning experience for the researcher as he seeks solutions to the problem. Additionally, it has the potential to develop and expand his powers, capacities, and thinking abilities.
- **Future Researchers.** This study would aid them in future research on student leaders' experiences. This study would also serve as a foundation for their research projects, providing them with data to develop questions for their studies.

E. Delimitations and Limitations

This study was conducted to understand the experiences of the student leader's in facing the new normal, specifically on what are the difficulties they encountered in facing the new normal, what are the ways they undertook in order to overcome their leadership difficulties, and what personal developments they have gained in overcoming those difficulties.

This study used a descriptive phenomenology research design and method. Key Informant Interview (KII) was used to gather data. In addition, methods introduced by Creswell (2013) was utilized in analyzing the data from the transcribed answers during the interview of the participant's descriptions of their real-life experiences. The study analyzed the data from the transcribed answers during the interview of the participant's descriptions of their real-life experiences.

The participants of this study were chosen from the selected public school in Banga, namely Banga National High School. The participants were chosen through predetermined criteria, which the researcher used to identify and select the participants.

F. Definition of Terms

In order for the readers to understand some concept of this research, the following terms are operationally defined:

- **Difficulties.** This refers to a time when a person faces trials in dealing with their duties and responsibilities. It is also a condition or situation wherein a person faces a specific problem that is difficult to deal with.
- **Leadership.** This refers to the ability of an individual or a group of individuals to influence and guide followers or other members of an organization.
- **New Normal.** This refers to the current situation, which is different from what has been experienced or done before but was expected to become usual or typical.
- **Student Leaders.** This refers to those students who are responsible, fair-minded, positive, and caring representatives of the student body. They actively demonstrate, promote and encourage involvement in creating a positive whole school community.

G. Organization of the Study

The first chapter of the study describes the problem and why it is essential to perform the thesis research. This enables the researcher to address the issues that have arisen. The justification that exposes the actual problem, the thesis objectives, and the literature that concludes why the study is needed are all included in this chapter. When writing Chapter 1, it was anticipated that the research questions would answer the problems stated in the rationale. This chapter also serves as a resource for school administrators, teachers, beneficiaries, students, researchers, and future researchers in dealing with student-mother issues.

Chapter 2 is the thesis study's backbone; here, we can see the benefits, the problems, and the linked literature that explains why we were undertaking the study. This chapter was crucial in determining the actual problem of the research study, as well as compensating for the respondent's responses to the literature and related studies. Furthermore, it specifies the problem that must be addressed during the thesis research. This will also support the respondents' claims and make reading the entire study chapter more valid.

The synergy of the thesis study in Chapter 3 provides energy on where to begin and what tools must be used to complete the investigation. This is where researchers can look at the study's methods, such as how the researcher completed it and the techniques used to make the thesis more realistic. The research design is one of the essential tools that can be seen in this chapter, as it will show the reader what design is being used to make the study look less futile. The study's sequence is more evident in this chapter; it provides promises of ethical consideration and trustworthiness, implying that the respondents will not benefit from the doubt.

The outcomes of the study's problems are presented in Chapter 4, which refers to the expectation and reality after reviewing the results derived from each respondent's responses. The study's findings are the most critical portion of the chapter since they show whether the thesis is successful or not. The results, on the other hand, would reveal how the researcher supported the issues raised in the study and the absence of proof in some of the research studies indicated in Chapter 2. The tools mentioned in each chapter will compensate for the tools utilized throughout the chapter. When the data is validated, it is clear that the respondents answered the study questions. This chapter will determine the study's effectiveness.

Chapter 5 is where the results are interpreted, and it is an essential component of the chapter because it broadens the reader's and future researcher's viewpoints. This also covers the implications for practice, emphasizing the teacher's need to practice handling student difficulties. Implications for future research are a one-way street to enlighten the study's flaws and broaden the scope of an issue. Overall, with the help of the entire chapter, it will provide an exquisite discussion and conclusion to the thesis study's disparities, therefore sufficing the remedies to the genuine difficulties of student leaders.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter explores the literature and studies which encompass relevant information to this study. This review of literature and studies provide an understanding of the large discussion on the difficulties experienced by student leaders in facing the new normal such as the difficulties they encountered during their leadership journey, the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties, and the personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties.

A. Difficulties Faced by Student Leaders

A school leader directs a school and is responsible for its administration or management, either alone or with a team, such as a school council. Furthermore, according to Eurydice (2013), the role of leaders may include organizational, pedagogical, and educational responsibilities, and organizational, pedagogical, and instructional obligations may be part of a leader's position. Depending on the conditions, school administrators may be relied upon to arrange scheduling, curriculum implementation, extracurricular activities, testing, and teacher assessment. Leaders may have financial obligations as well as teaching responsibilities in some circumstances.

In addition, the phrase "school leadership" has evolved over the last twenty to thirty years to reflect changes in the function of leaders. A movement may be seen in many education systems, from a more administrative and bureaucratic function to one more involved in working with teachers and other personnel to enhance school achievements (Adams & Gaetane, 2011).

In addition, more specifically, school leaders' roles are evolving from guiding the school's learning program to a more complicated and polished approach as facilitators of the collective work of professionals at and surrounding their schools. The establishment of collaborative cultures is at the heart of this new function, called collaborative professionalism (Hargreaves, 2020).

Students continually complain of poor residential and catering facilities conditions, increased fees, inadequate representation in the senate, and poor communication with university management (Republic of Kenya, 2014).

Kenny et al. (2013) asserted that students in higher institutions of learning have numerous challenges. Therefore, students' counselors and trainers ought to consistently evaluate students' concerns and provide accessible information and services that would be useful in easing their concerns. Accordingly, workshops on negotiation skills, administration of student crises, time and stress management, career choices, and development could be offered to student leaders to aid their academic work.

Additionally, the desirable leadership attributes incorporate the capacity to designate, motivate and communicate well (Yukl, 2012). A student leader should have strong leadership, organizational, and public speaking skills. He/she should be deadline-oriented, able to build consensus, and help bring the diverse student body together as a community through programmed and non-programmed events. Collaboration enhances leadership skills. It is of the essence for student leaders to work productively in gatherings, acknowledge feedback and admit mistakes when working with others. Student leaders who succeed just when working alone will battle in the work environment and beyond, as the more significant part of professions require cooperation. Student leaders can build up the skills necessary to viably work with others in several ways, including sorting out and taking part in community outreach, team-based projects, and co-curricular activities that promote integration among students.

On the other hand, Bosire et al. (2013) argued that the ultimate bearers of the challenges experienced in public universities are the student leaders and university managers who have to adjust their expectations according to the prevailing conditions.

Furthermore, the pressure is constant, the options are limited, and sleepless nights are typical for school leaders operating in these complex and chaotic circumstances. Staff meetings, coffee catch-ups, and corridor discussions with coworkers that used to make up a school day are no longer there. Those key, informal moments when social bonds are formed, and leadership is demonstrated vanish. Parents, students, and instructors now live in a twilight education world, waiting for standard service to return or hoping for a new normal to provide stability, continuity, and reassurance. Furthermore, this is a perfect storm with sloppy leadership. In a crisis, leaders must respond quickly and with foresight, but also with serious analysis of options, repercussions, and side effects of actions taken (Netolicky, 2020).

Moreover, school leadership practices have changed dramatically and possibly forever due to the Covid-19 pandemic. School leadership has rotated on its axis due to the pandemic, and it is unlikely to return to "normal" anytime soon, if at all. The fundamentals of excellent leadership, such as having a clear vision, developing others, managing people, and building capacity. The information also alludes to the necessity of context-responsive leadership, meaning that COVID-19 has caused a shift in school leadership practices (Harris, 2020).

Lastly, in this pandemic, the slogan "connect to learn, learn to connect" characterizes the daily reality of students and instructors attempting to collaborate. As a result, school leaders will need to be more digitally aware and well-informed. Furthermore, COVID-19 has sparked a wave of commercial opportunism, with a push to acquire technology solutions to today's challenges. As a result, school administrators must be picky about the digital goods they use and mindful of striking a balance between technology and pedagogy in their classrooms (Hargreaves, 2020).

B. Ways to Overcome Leadership Difficulties

Universities and colleges have student councils, and higher education institutions have student councils. Educational institutions have developed various forms of leadership development—ways for developing and disseminating the potential of student leaders. The driving force behind student councils' responsibilities is shaping or forming students' minds. Although the agendas of higher education institutions differ, there is a supposed unanimity in the goal: to provide venues for debating, educating, and, perhaps, changing the way leaders treat their people (Dugan, 2013).

According to Garlejo (2016), every college or institution has a student council that serves as the school's ultimate student group. Its principal responsibility is to ensure that all student rights and welfare are always protected and encouraged. The Student Council's duties include developing school spirit and promoting the general welfare of students, advising the university/college President on student matters, affairs, and activities of distinctly intercollegiate concern, adopting its by-laws for internal and general government, coordinating student activities, and exercising such powers and performing such acts of duties as the school authorities may from time-to-time delegate to it.

On the other hand, training is an organized activity that imparts knowledge and skills specially packaged to promote student leaders' performance. It is an exercise that provides student leaders with the skills necessary to undertake their roles effectively. A university exists to prepare students intellectually and transform them holistically (Kristin et al., 2011).

Additionally, the key to unlocking these challenges is harnessing student leaders, enhancing their leadership capacity to enable them to provide effective student services, and positioning them at the center of the management of student affairs. Such leaders may assist university management by improving staff and student relationships, reducing indiscipline cases, and improving performance in both academic and co-curricular programs (UNICEF, 2013).

Moreover, Gacutan (2015) stated that leaders of various student organizations on each campus played critical roles in school improvement. They are regarded as a potent supply of human resources that the institution uses for instruction and research, as in school management. This is especially true with students, who are regarded as the most vital educational community members. Students, despite their youth, are aware of the numerous issues that confront their school lives and futures. As a result, they should take the initiative to give answers to such issues, offering them opportunities to succeed because they want to; they implement their plans and mobilize their efforts within their capacities. Students' development will be aided, and the school's reputation will be enhanced.

In addition, student leaders who see their subordinates as equals are more effective, according to the stories. This is because, as one leader put it, "acting as a good example while remaining humble about it makes one effective." Another informant agreed, saying that a leader is first among equals and can inspire others. While the job is being done, use your voice to console others. Furthermore, the narratives have shown that student leaders value their commitment to colleges and universities. Being elected to the position means their initiative will serve and inspire other students (Miles, 2010).

Lastly, according to the study by Murage et al. (2019), in many parts of the world, including Kenya, effective administration of student affairs in public universities continues to be a significant problem for university administrators and student leaders. Student unrest and strikes are commonplace at public universities. However, creative measures to reduce these occurrences have been adopted, such as including student leaders in the governance of institutions of higher learning. Furthermore, the rationale of the study was to analyze the challenges faced by student leaders in managing student affairs in public universities in Kenya.

C. Personal Developments Gained by Student Leaders in Overcoming Difficulties

As regards another issue and point of view presented by the school leaders, namely school and classroom conditions, the goal for school leaders was to create and sustain a competitive school, through school improvement plans, by involving themselves in setting professional standards, stimulating the teaching staff intellectually, by offering professional development opportunities and staff assessment. Furthermore, sharing actions makes collaboration more accessible, and valuable ideas may arise from sharing best practices and successful outcomes among teachers. Sharing leadership is an excellent possibility for stimulating and authorizing others to make significant decisions (Ghergut, 2014).

Another thing is that the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that would nurture leadership improvement may not necessarily be tested in a formal examination and, therefore, not taken seriously by students. However, these students are relied upon to take up leadership roles in their institutions and society as they enter the labor force (Kristin et al., 2011).

Moreover, leadership concepts and skills are woven into an educational curriculum that uses instructional strategies which promote and support experiential and active learning, enhance not only the learning process but also students' interpersonal effectiveness, their ability to positively engage and collaborate across diverse perspectives, and their sense of self-efficacy for making a positive difference in the world. In addition, education that promotes leadership development uses assessments that measure the big picture of holistic education, including critical thinking, informative decision-making, perseverance, problem-solving, creativity, curiosity, compassion, integrity, and moral responsibility, such as simulation-based assessments (Hammer, 2013).

Furthermore, the role of educators is to function as mentors and facilitators to guide and support their student leaders to reach maturity and to grow to be kind, compassionate, and thoughtful individuals. Furthermore, it advocated that student leadership development is the progression through which a person exposed to transformations develops more complex behaviors instigated by overcoming growing encounters or challenges in life through creative thinking and problem-solving, pointing out that the schooling phase has the most significant impact on their student experiences, among which, student leadership development is thought to be one of the most fundamental responsibilities of the educational institutions (Mozhgan et al., 2011).

On the other hand, developing the leadership skills of young people will assist them in overcoming individual and social difficulties in solidarity and ultimately lead them to contribute to the development of society. Young people need opportunities to take leadership roles to improve their leadership skills. For this reason, unlike theoretical knowledge, leadership development programs should provide actual leadership experience, a practice-based infrastructure and hands-on learning activities (Cress et al., 2015).

In addition, the general concept of leadership does not correspond to the performance of a single individual but instead to the joint forces driving educational institutions and society as a whole toward their future. Therefore, it is essential to instill in students with principles and values linked to leadership at very young ages. Educators should allow their students to build resilience, kindness, and empathy, which are capacities leading to mental strength. Additionally, they need to be exposed to the significance of taking calculated risks, embracing change, and being willing and eager to move forward while respecting and celebrating diversity. Leadership development should be included in educational curriculum design for students to be exposed to leadership ideas and practices (Komives et al., 2014).

Lastly, Wingenbach et al. (2015) suggested that secondary school students can develop leadership skills via decision-making, getting along with others, learning the organization of self, self-awareness, and working with groups through participating in many youth leadership organizations in school and community activities. Furthermore, it is helpful to examine leadership during childhood and adolescence as what occurs during the developmental years can impact the leadership behaviors exhibited later in the workplace as an adult.

D. Synthesis

Student leaders are crucial in facilitating the organization, programs, and activities to be implemented in school. Thus, leadership is a skill that student leaders need to possess, including planning, productivity, effectiveness, and outcomes. However, despite being a good leader, difficulties happen, and it is considered natural. It is a leader's responsibility to take action and develop an effective response to the situation.

During the pandemic, student leaders deal with various difficulties, specifically in managing their time, and need help to produce an effective plan to follow safe and measurable protocols. The new average education was indeed a challenge, continuously dealing with challenges with vast adjustments. Furthermore, the journey of the student leaders to achieve good governance was something that should be appreciated.

Therefore, student leaders can handle responsibilities and appropriate responses to the difficulties ahead of them. This study inspires all student leaders to know that difficulties are part of developing an excellent leadership style.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methods of research used during the study. It includes the research design employed in exploring the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal. Furthermore, it discusses the overall design of the study: the participants, the sources of data, data gathering procedure, analysis, and ethical considerations in the conduct of this study.

A. Research Design

This study used descriptive phenomenology. The descriptive phenomenological approach is the chosen approach for this study to focus on the individuals or groups of people's experiences within the scope of the study. The focus is on gaining insights and familiarity for later investigation. According to Creswell (2013), when doing descriptive qualitative phenomenological research is an approach where it focuses on the commonality of such lived experiences within a particular group. The goal of this design is to arrive at a description of nature with a particular phenomenon.

B. Role of the Researcher

This study allowed the researcher, an education student, to enhance his skills and suffice his knowledge. The role of the researcher was to document the study for the readers (documenter) and also to enable them to understand (enabler) what leadership difficulties are encountered by the student leaders, how they overcome those difficulties and their personal developments in overcoming those difficulties. Furthermore, the researcher's participation in seeking to reach the study participant's ideas, feelings, and experiences is required, as this is a complex undertaking that entails asking individuals to talk about topics that are potentially highly personal to them. Another primary role of the researcher was safeguarding participants' data, such as information and answers. The mechanisms for safeguarding participants must be appropriately communicated to them and authorized by a competent research ethical review board before the study begins. Lastly, it is a must role of the researcher to seek advice from an experienced and reliable qualitative researcher before embarking on and publishing the study.

C. Research Participants

As descriptive phenomenology approached to explore individuals' lived experiences, Roulston (2010) purports that the researcher identified participants from 3-5 participants who can talk about the personal experience they have the time in real-life experiences under review. It includes criteria to be needed in the study. For this reason, student leaders who had experienced leadership difficulties in the new normal and were willing and able to talk about it were sought for this study, which is included in the said criteria based on the definition presented.

D. Locale of the Study

This study was conducted within Banga, South Cotabato's selected public school, Banga National High School. The study participants were intentionally chosen considering their position in Supreme Student Government (SSG).

Banga is a first-class municipality in the Province of South Cotabato. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 89,164 people. Banga is linked by a concrete national highway road from General Santos City to the East and Cotabato City to the West. The town is known for its spacious town plaza, and its public market is situated in the heart of the town and is ideally signified.

Banga National High School was created through Republic Act 6991, known as the Creation of Banga National High School. The creation of the school was realized through the efforts of the constituents of Banga, Mayor Mary Lou M. Solomon, and with the assistance of late former congressman Hilario Le De Pedro III. The institution was established in January 1991.

In 1993, the school applied for National Recognition, and it was under Region XI Davao City. Saunas supervised the disbursement of funds at first, and Mrs. Lenie Javellana trained the bookkeeper and the disbursing officer. Then, in 1994, teachers' salaries were under the Division Office but were again supervised by Miss Linda Isidro at NHS.

The institution went through trials and difficulties until concrete facilities were granted through the late Gov. Hilario De Pedro, the municipal officials, and Congresswoman Daisy Avance Fuentes. Since then, government agencies have sponsored more classrooms here and abroad. Several administrators took part in the endeavor for the development of the school.

In 2013-2014, the school organized some intervention programs, such as an information drive and counseling services, as part of the Guidance Office Program and feeding program for malnourished students. Other programs include Gulayan sa Paaralan, Youth Entrepreneurship and Cooperativism in Schools (YECS-BNHS), Solid Waste Management, MTAP, Reading Program, The School Greening Program (NDEP) Convention on the Rights of the Child, and RACRAS. There is also Boy Scouting which is very active.

Banga National High School aims to uphold quality education. The school continues to develop the student's talents and skills in academics and sports. In modern times it hopes to achieve modern instruction through computers and networking.

Fig. 1: Map of Banga South Cotabato

**BANGA NATIONAL
HIGH SCHOOL**

E. Research Instrument

The study used an interview guide in the exploration of the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal. Guide questions are all drafted to extract the experiences of the participants. The interviewer used the interview guide questionnaire during the critical informant interview. Roulston's (2010) interview guide provides evidence for claims about what happens in our world. Thus, interviewing was chosen as the instrument for this study to elicit evidence to answer the research questions and, through careful analysis of the words shared by participants in their descriptions of their experiences, garner the more prominent themes that the evidence supports.

The defense panel reviewed and approved the following interview guide to ensure validity and congruence with the research questions. The contents of the interview guide are all about answering the research questions that are relevant and align with the teachers' experiences in the new mode of teaching.

F. Data Collection

The data and information were collected through the use of key informant interviews. An interview is composed of three questions mainly formulated to ask about the difficulties they encounter during their leadership journey, how they undertake to overcome those difficulties, and what personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties:

The researcher prepared a letter such as Permission Letter for the Instructor, Informed consent for the participants, Participants' Agreement Form, Parents' Consent Form, and Student Leader Adviser Consent Form. The researcher asked permission from his instructor to interview his selected participants and ask for approval. When the instructor approved the letter, the researcher printed it and held a photocopy to serve as his reference.

The researcher sent a letter of informed consent, which informed the participant that the researcher conducted an interview and provided information about the obstacles they encountered during their leadership journey, what are the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties, and what personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties. It was followed by the Participants Agreement Form, which comprised the participant's and researcher's agreement for the conduct of the interview and transcription of the data collected.

The researcher sends the Parents Consent Form to the parents and the Student Leader Adviser Form, which contains the agreement between the researcher and the student leader's parents and adviser indicating that they are allowing their students to participate in the study. After that, the researcher started to conduct a virtual interview with his participants, and the researcher took a picture and recorded the interview, serving as his guide. The researcher analyzed the data that has been gathered.

G. Analysis of the Data

A descriptive Qualitative Research Design was used in this study to relate two methods of data analysis by Colaizzi (2013) and Moustakas (2012). The methods used the data by reduction of information.

After the interview, the data gathered were transcribed. All the transcribed interviews were presented to the participants for them to validate.

Methods Introduced by Colaizzi and Moustakas were used to analyze data from the transcribed answer during the interview of the participant's descriptions of their lived experiences. The interview transcriptions were coded and determined the lines of significant statements. Moustakas (2012) quoted and combined themes or textural descriptions that answered the question about what the participants have experienced. The themes were regrouped to draw cluster themes (Colaizzi, 2013) and Moustakas (2012). These cluster themes answered how they experienced the conditions, situations, or context. Finally, the emergent themes were drawn, which are the combinations of textural and structural descriptions (Moustakas, 2012). This revealed the essence of the lived experiences of student leaders. The emergent themes were the basis for discussion and recommendation of the study. Referrals of emergent themes to participants were also done to validate the data.

H. Trustworthiness

Data was obtained through an informative interview with the participants at a mutually convenient time. Interviews were done one-on-one through face-to-face interviews with the interviewer and the selected participants establishing a pleasant fellowship. They were considering and also following the safety health protocols to ensure safety against the pandemic. The researcher recorded the interview using a cellphone/laptop and manually.

The interview was conducted according to the interview procedure. The interview began with an introduction to the interview mechanics, focusing on the ethical issues highlighted in this study, as well as the interview methods and duration. The following was presented to the identified participants: Informed Consent Form, Participant's Agreement Form, Parents' Consent Form, Student Leader Advisers Consent Form, and the Interview Protocol for the Participants.

Before the interview, the elements and substance of the interview questionnaire were addressed. During the actual interview, the researcher asked for detailed accounts of the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal.

Their lived experiences are divided into information about the difficulties they encounter during their leadership journey, the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties, and what personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties. For emphasis and clarification, follow-up questions were asked.

The researcher kept track of the exit interview data, which included the precise date, the start and finish times, and the respondents' names. This was done to track the duration of the interview with the respondents.

I. Ethical Considerations

Ethical challenges arise in each phase of the research process in the study. The study involves collecting and sharing data about the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal. First, getting permission for participation from the students themselves and an adviser is essential. Before the conduct of the actual gathering of data, the researcher explained to the participants the purpose of the study. Included in the permission are a clear explanation of what the study entails, the potential risks, and confirmation of anonymity. It also makes clear to the participants that they can choose to discontinue their participation at any time without penalty. The researcher then explained that the signed form needed to be returned for the student to participate in the interviews. After the research participants are selected, the researcher meets each participant individually. Furthermore, it was made clear to the participants that the purpose of this study was not to evaluate their doings of anything. The nature of the interview questions only provides a focus for participants to share their experiences as student leaders facing the new normal.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

This chapter presents the themes drawn from the analysis of the responses during the key informant interviews (KII). In identifying themes, the researcher transcribed the audio version of the interview. From the transcript of the interviews, significant statements were extracted. These were utilized in response to the main research questions on the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal.

Since there were several significant statements in the study, caution was used to ensure that the statements were relevant. The organization of the discussion in this chapter is based on the emergent themes which significantly answered the research questions.

A. What are the difficulties being encountered by the student leaders during their leadership journey?

Table 1: Presents the difficulties that student leaders encounter during their leadership journey.

Emergent Themes	Clustered Themes
Disinterest and Apathy	Non-participation of members during meetings or assemblies. Difficulty in gathering participants. Loss of interest among members. Non-participation of members in the activities conducted.
Communication Barrier	Lack of communication among members. Difficulty in conducting meetings due to connectivity problems. Some officers could not participate because they had no internet connection. Lack of communication due to connectivity issues. Difficulty in Disseminating or relaying Information. Unsteady or intermittent Internet Connections. Problem in reaching out to the other officers.
Financial Inadequacy	Inadequacy of budget for the organization.
Inadequacy of budget for the organization	Limitations in the activities due to health protocol.
Pandemic-Related Obstacles	Enactment of rules is complex due to social distancing and health protocols. Adjustment complexities brought by the new normal.
Hurdles in Implementation and Service Delivery	Difficulty in conducting and sustaining programs. Difficulty with Classroom organization. Problems with the Implementation of rules.
A Pile-Load Of Tasks	Loaded with requirements to comply and submit. Conflicts with other equally important activities.
Parental Prohibitions	Parents do not give their consent to their children. Parental Limitations and not giving consent.

➤ *Disinterest and Apathy*

As the new normal arises and it results in numerous changes in all aspects of life, most student leaders lose their interest and motivation to do something in their roles as student leaders. Apathy and disinterest are generally perceived as not having concern or interest in a particular phenomenon. From a scholarly perspective, apathy is related to motivation, which means "without motivation" and refers to "a state of motivational apathy in which students harbor little to no reason to engage in classroom learning activities; it is a motivational deficit that is strongly associated with maladaptive functioning" (Cheon & Reeve, 2015, p. 99). Most student leaders lose the courage to participate and attend their gatherings. As such, participants

expressed their perceptions on why students like them experience difficulties in their roles as student leaders. Rosemarie and Robert had the exact reasons they lost interest in their roles. Rosemarie explained that they needed help gathering the participants for their meeting since other students and officers were unavailable. Robert also said that due to the current situation, there are times that they lose the courage and interest to do their part as a student leader.

So ng isa pagid kay ng hindi face to face na makitanay ang mga ano ang iban nga mga officers nga under sa amon nang hindi sila kaayo ga participate kay isa pa gid indi pa gid sila namon makita kag indi namon maakigan man so far amu man lang na. (P3/19-22-Rosemarie)

(Another thing is that, since it is not face-to-face to meet up with other officers who are under us, they need to be more participative, and we cannot see them, and we cannot scold them so far, that is all.)

Another participant shared his insight on how he faced the loss of courage in his responsibility as a student leader. He shared that there are times when they need more interest in their roles.

There are sometimes nga madulaan na matak-an na madulaan na gana. (P2/86-87-Robert)

(There are times that we lose courage and interest.)

In addition, due to the changes brought by the new normal, only some student leaders are allowed to interact and attend their meetings or gatherings. Michelle and Robert expressed their insights about the other student leaders' unavailability during meetings and gatherings. The two of them had expressed their experiences when there was no pandemic compared to the present new normal.

Kung mag held kami sang meeting namun indi available ang tanan. (P1/35-Michelle)

(When we held a meeting, everyone was not available.)

Robert gave the idea that they encounter the unavailability or absence of the other student leaders when they have gatherings or meetings.

Maybe ano lang sa participants lang kay gamay lang na pwede ang participants na ma kuha namon pero in conducting subong hindi na sya kayo budlay unlike dati. (P2/25-27-Robert)

(Maybe to the participants because the participants we can gather are few, but now it is easier than before.)

➤ *Communication Barrier*

The effect of the new normal brought dramatic changes to everyone's lives, and one of the affected parts is the mode of communication. Students and teachers may have technical barriers while communicating due to a lack of technological expertise and semantic barriers during communication (Perreault & Waldman 2012).

Communication should be given importance during this time since it serves as a gateway to communicate and give important points or reminders to those student leaders who need to participate and attend their gatherings. Most student leaders need help conducting their meetings, disseminating information, and encountering trouble with internet connection. Michelle and Nielvin emphasized that the main obstacle they

encounter during this new normal is the mode of communication wherein they need to communicate effectively with other officers.

Well communication gid ang main problem subong. (1/26-Michelle)

(Well, communication is the main problem nowadays.)

Melvin also expressed his idea that due to the pandemic, they need more communication among the organization's members since other members live in outlying areas.

Ahh subong nga may pandemic, number one gid nga problem nga ma encounter namun is lack of communication gid sya kay especially kung mag pa meeting kami ang iban sa amun is lagyo (P4/18-20-Nielvin)

(Now that the pandemic is present, the number one problem we encounter is the need for more communication, primarily when we conduct meetings with others far away.)

Another participant pointed out that they need help in disseminating important information.

Daw budlay maka communicate kag mabudlay ma relay ang mga info. nga halin sa itaas. (P4/20-21-Nielvin)

(It is hard to communicate and relay information that came from above.)

In addition, Melvin also shared his idea that other members encounter connectivity problems when they conduct meetings.

Oomm isa gid na sya sa mga problema namun so kay biskan mag meeting kami daw ang iban daw ma intindihan man pero kay chappy sya indi gid sya ma anu maayu. (P4/31-33-Nielvin)

(Yes, it is one of our problems since when we conduct meetings, others cannot easily understand since they are Chappy, and we cannot understand them clearly.)

Other participants have pointed out their difficulties when they conduct meetings and activities since other officers need the opportunity to access good quality phones and the struggles between the availability of internet connections among them. Robert and Rosemarie expressed their struggles with time management and the hardships in accessing internet connections among other officers.

Kung may online activity for all kasi ang possible na face to face is mga selected students lang gd pero kung for all students gd syempre naga struggle kami kay syempre sa officer namon di tanan magkaroon ng internet connection like sometimes di tanan maka join like sometimes mag conduct kami sang meetings. (P2/32-35-Robert)

(When we have online activity, if possible, to have face-to-face, the students are selected, but if it is intended for all, we are struggling most especially with other officers, since few of us can access an internet connection just like when we conduct meetings sometimes.)

Rosemarie also expressed that they encounter difficulty reaching out to the other officers.

Ahh ng ano ahh mas nabudlayan ko subong ang mag ano man mag reach out sa iban nga officers. (P3/46-47-Rosemarie)

(Now, we need help to reach out to the other officers.)

On the other hand, Rosemarie shared that the other members cannot attend the meetings since they do not have load to access the conference.

May ara man kuy ng sa internet connection then sa iban ng sa time nila kay ang iban indi man ka attend gid kay indi available kay wla sila load so pero madayun gid gyapon kay more than man kami sa meeting. (P3/79-81-Rosemarie)

(The internet connection and then the time since others cannot attend because they are unavailable due to lack of loads, but it will be conducted since we are more than those who attend the meeting.)

Due to the changes brought by the new normal, the transfer from correspondence to web-based and telecommunication systems in distance learning has created complications. Some of these are the need for training and guidance in an online context, unawareness of new technology, lack of satisfactory technology, participants defying technological changes, difficulty accessing the internet, and difficulty analyzing teachers' perspectives and delivering systems (Isman & Altinay, 2015).

➤ *Financial Inadequacy*

One of the main problems student leaders encounter is financial inadequacy, primarily in supporting their programs and projects. They need help finding their source of funds to sustain their needs in implementing their desired programs and activities. These days, our economic growth is slowly decreasing, and most encounter financial hardships. Michelle shared her insight about their difficulty finding a budget to support their activities and programs. Since during this time, it is challenging enough to raise funds in order to support the expenses of the organization.

Then sa budget man namun indi abi kami maka pangita sang budget subong. (P1/26-27-Michelle)

(Then to our budget, we cannot look for budget now.)

➤ *Inadequacy of Budget for the Organization*

The student leaders need a budget to support their programs, but due to the changes brought by the new average, student leaders need more funding to help their organization. Student leaders aim to provide different activities and programs to impact the schools and students positively. But the primary consideration is the need for more funds to support their plans and to implement their agenda. Michelle expresses her idea that they need help to quickly raise and locate funds since their actions are limited by the new normal.

Kung mag interact kami dire sa school may ara gid sang indi sang sugtan lalo na tung mga indi pa fully vaccinated. (P1/45-46-Michelle)

(When we interact here at school, some officers are restricted, especially those who are not fully vaccinated.)

➤ *Pandemic-Related Obstacles*

The current pandemic is an obstacle that affects student leaders in implementing their rules and plans. An important finding regarding crisis leadership is that what constitutes effective leadership often changes over the crisis (Hannah et al., 2014). Another thing is that, since they are teenagers, they are not allowed to go out, and they don't have the freedom to do whatever they want. They face adjustments, and their actions are limited

due to the limitations brought by the new normal. Michelle and Robert provide their insights on how the pandemic changes their usual ways as student leaders compared to the average days when the pandemic is absent.

Like subong na year kuya, ano abi kay budlay abi sya subong na year na mag anu kami sang rules kuya kay indi sya face to face classes. (P1/16-17-Michelle)

(Like this year, it is difficult now to enact rules since it is not face-to-face.)

Robert gave the same idea that they adjust to the new standard set-up and the changes brought by it.

Syempre budlay gid subong actually until now naga adjust pa kami sa what we call this sa new normal nga set up. (P2/59-60-Robert)

(It is hard for now, and until now, we are adjusting to the new standard set-up.)

➤ *Hurdles in Implementation and Service Delivery*

Since the pandemic is present, most student leaders need help conducting and sustaining their programs. Student leaders don't have the opportunity to take action easily since the limitations surrounding them and the threat of the pandemic towards their health are considered alarming. Most of them also encounter hardships in classroom organization and in implementing rules. Robert and Rosemarie shared that it is challenging for them to sustain a particular program during this time. At the same time, they cannot easily organize a specific program due to the limitations of the pandemic.

Siguro first and foremost syempre to conduct programs projects and activities specifically mga programs na gusto namon I sustain like under the project na palayok that project started sa time ni kuya Leo until now gina sustain sya for sustainability. (P2/19-22-Robert)

(First and foremost, we primarily conduct programs, projects and activities, specifically the programs we like to sustain, like the Project Palayok that started during the time of Kuya Leo until now; we maintained it for sustainability.)

Additionally, Rosemarie, a hardworking student leader, expresses her insight about their struggles in implementing their rules and other concerns. Since as student leaders need to have the initiatives to organize and implement their plans.

Uhhh first kay syempre kay pandemic subong ang perti gid kabudlay is ang pag organize sang mga ano sang classroom. (P3/17-18-Rosemarie)

(First, because it is pandemic now, it is difficult for us to organize things in the classroom.)

In addition, Rosemarie also shared that they encounter difficulty in implementing their new principles or rules.

Paano mag implement gid sang imo mga bag o nga principles or mga rules. (P3/18-19-Rosemarie)

(On how to implement the new principles or rules.)

➤ *A Pile-Load of Tasks*

Being a student leader is quite challenging since they face different responsibilities and have been given enough opportunities to perform their roles as a student leader. As conditions shift and new needs emerge, leaders must be flexible and adaptive (Smith & Riley, 2012). Student leaders are loaded with different requirements that they must comply with, and they have family matters that must be dealt with. Furthermore, most of them inevitably encounter conflicts in their responsibilities and issues as student leaders and students. Robert, a responsible student leader, had expressed his experience of managing his time in dealing with his responsibility and academic matters.

Example may ara activities last time and supposed to be tapuson ko pa ang mga requirements ko so parang anu lang man gina control lang man nga basi ma sobrahan. (P2/48-50-Robert)

(For example, when we had activities last time and I was supposed to finish my other requirements, I control my time so that I could go on time.)

Another student leader Nielvin, also shared his experiences about the conflicts in his academics since he cannot manage it properly due to numerous activities being given and, at the same time, how he prioritizes the things that need to be done first.

May ara kami sang activity sa academic nga daw indi namun ma supalpalan tanan kaya daw ga conflict gid sya so maka pili gid kami kung anu ang priority namun although nga amu sina ang amun nga mga teacher. (P4/45-47-Nielvin)

(When we have an activity in academics that we think we cannot do, it is a conflict, so in that way, we can choose our priorities, although that is the way of our teachers.)

➤ *Parental Prohibitions*

Since the pandemic threat is very alarming, most parents are concerned with the safety of their children's health. So, most student leaders encounter limitations that their parents are setting, and at the same time, their parents do not allow them to do the things they need to do. Parents avoid school and feel hindered from taking an active role in their child's education when discomfort exists (Georgis, et. al. 2014). Parents' main goal is to ensure their children's health, but it can be considered a hindrance for them to do their part as student leaders. Melvin said they could only efficiently finish a specific task with the help of the other officers since other officers are being restricted by their parents from attending their meetings or gatherings.

Ah maliban sina is syempre kay iban indi man sugtan kay tungod sa pandemic indi man sugtan nga mag gwa or indi sugtan sang parents nila so isa gid na sya sa problems namun kay indi namun kumbaga indi namun makaya ang isa ka activity kung kulang kami. (P4/24-27-Nielvin)

(Except for that, others are restricted because of the pandemic, and they are not allowed to go out, or their parents do not allow them to go out. So, it is one of our problems because we can only finish the activity if we are complete.)

Rosemarie has pointed out the same worry that other student leaders don't have the freedom to go out since the pandemic is threatening their parents.

Kung para lang sa akon ang first nga indi gid sila pag sugtan kay syempre pandemic so ang iban abi nga parents nila nang strict bala haw. (P3/27-28-Rosemarie)

(For me, the first thing is that they are restricted because it is a pandemic, so the other parents are strict.)

B. What are the ways undertaken by the student leaders to overcome their leadership difficulties?

Table 2: Presents the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties.

Emergent Themes	Clustered Themes
Staying Connected	Communicate with other significant officers. Conduct Online Meetings or inform class presidents. Ensure information updates and make constant reminders.
Maximizing Alternatives	Look for other ways, such as House Visitation. Make updates or leave Announcements. Utilize other forms of social media to maximize communication and participation.
Reaching Out to Others	Solicit funds and generate income through initiatives.
Looking into Positivity	Be optimistic and motivate oneself despite the challenges. Encourage the members about the purpose and result of the activity.
Taking A Breather	Find time to rest or relax.
Wearing Another's Shoes	Establish a better relationship with members or co-officers. Understand the situation of others by exempting them from the activities.
Following the Courtesy Call	Asking for Permission and consent properly from the administration or concerned persons.

➤ *Staying Connected*

Most of the student leaders encounter difficulty in communication, in that way being connected with using their initiatives to use different platforms. One thing that they perform is to conduct meeting online and ensure they can communicate and connect with the significant officers effectively. Two participants, Michelle and Nielvin, had expressed how they found ways to share and stay associated with other student leaders—ensuring that they connected to updates and that all of the officers were informed of the announcements being given.

Well naga communicate nalang kami nga mga major officers. (P1/51-Michelle)

(Well, we communicate with the major officers.)

Moreover, Michelle also shared that for them to be connected, they often hold online meetings and contact the presidents in each room.

Mga anu nalang naga conduct nalang kami sang mga activities then naga hold kami sang mga Gmeet. Then Gina contact nalang namun ang mga president each room. (P1/18-20-Michelle)

(We conduct activities through Google Meet. Then we contact or reach out to the presidents in each room.)

In addition, Melvin also shared how he communicates with other officers and how he uses his initiative to inform his co-officers about the upcoming plans for their organization.

So ang gina himo namon sina is, una palang daw gina pa balo na namon una palang para maka prepare ang mga iban nga officers. (P4/76-77-Nielvin)

(So, the usual thing that we do is to inform the other officers to be prepared.)

➤ *Maximizing Alternatives*

Since the changes brought by the new normal are challenging, most of the student leaders maximize their ways to produce alternative solutions to cope with their activities. Given the increased complexity and diversity of situations requiring immediate solutions, academic leaders will make innovative decisions and respond to the needs (Al-Dabbagh, 2020). Even though most student leaders are teenagers, they are clever enough to perform and expand their ways towards their duties. Both Michelle and Robert expressed their insights on how they maximize their initiatives to conduct their activities.

Kag kung kis naga house to house kami. (P1/55-Michelle)

(Sometimes we conduct house to house.)

In addition, Michelle also shared her idea that they give announcements so that other student leaders are informed about the critical matters in their organization.

Announcement lang kung may mag lakat sa school like ligad dire may meeting. (P1/59-61-Michelle)

(We give announcements if they can go to school like yesterday, we have a meeting here.)

Additionally, Robert also shared how he utilizes the importance of technology in dealing with the limitations brought by the new normal.

Uhh, internet Naman subong mostly so why not let's maximize the use of social media, so naga conduct kami sang mga activities through online not just in Facebook but we are extending our social media just like Instagram Twitter and then hmm naga use din kami nang zoom or google meet for us to conduct activities together virtually. (P2/73-77-Robert)

(With internet now, why not maximize the use of social media, so we conduct activities online not just in Facebook but we are extending our social media platforms just like Instagram, Twitter and then we can use zoom or google meet for us to conduct our activities together virtually.)

➤ *Reaching Out to Others*

Due to the limitations of the new normal, one of the significant difficulties being encountered by student leaders is financial matters. So, the student leader finds an alternative way to support their economic instability. Michelle had expressed her insight about how they solicit funds for their programs or activities.

Man namun indi abi kami maka pangita sang budget subong pero last time sang December didtu lang kami naka kuha sang dako na budget kay naka solicit kami in a way nga nag caroling kami. (P1/27-28-Michelle)

(We cannot look for budget now, but last December, we solicit funds by conducting carolling.)

➤ *Looking into Positivity*

The new normal has negative impacts on the life of each individual. Most student leaders may encounter the negative side of life, especially in facing their responsibility as a leader. Still, they choose to look at the positive side, especially when they encounter trials in performing their roles as a student leader. Positive leadership requires the courage to be confident. It takes courage to introduce a new way of being or doing. In our new standard of hybrid or remote learning, leaders must be courageous enough to do what is suitable for

teachers and students (Joseph, 2020). One effective way for them is to motivate themselves since it is a powerful tool in setting an appropriate environment for them to grow. Both participants, Robert and Nielvin, shared their viewpoints on developing a positive mindset toward their challenges as student leaders.

Simple lang ng mga steps, siguro first and foremost to motivate me because I can only motivate or lead a particular group or this school or group of student leaders in this school ahh if I encourage myself. (P2/80-83-Robert)

(Steps are simple. First thing is to motivate me because, at the end of the day, I cannot encourage or lead a particular group or this school or group of student leaders without motivating myself.)

Another student leader pointed out that they encourage the other student leader who needs to attend their activities.

So ang gina himo namon dira is, daw gina encourage nalang sila namon pero ang pag encourage namon is in different way nang gina send namon kung ano kami ka happy sa mga activity nga gina himo namon samtang kami naga work as student leaders. (P4/96-99-Nielvin)

(So we encourage them and the way we encourage tis different. We send them on how happy we are in conducting our activities when we work as a student leader.)

➤ *Taking a Breather*

The responsibility of being a student leader is challenging in that it needs perseverance and ample time to perform its duties. Most of them are inevitably tired of doing their task and, at the same time, dealing with their academics and other important matters. Most of them are exhausted and lose the courage to create their plans, but they manage to rest before taking another step toward their task. Robert also expresses his insight on managing his time when he is tired of doing his responsibility.

Uhmm anu lang siguro take rest after take a rest balik naman liwat. (P2/87-88-Robert)

(Uhmm, take a rest, after taking a rest, go back to the usual.)

➤ *Wearing another's Shoes*

Student leaders also know how to consider the conditions of their co-officers since they have different priorities and tasks to deal with. In this way, student leaders can quickly create long-lasting friendships with their co-officers, and at the same time, they can quickly help one another when they encounter trials. Inevitably, most of them need help to perform their task in an organized manner, but they consider the part of the other student leaders. Michelle said that they interact and meet with others when there are meetings. In that way, they can socialize with them and develop friendships with them.

Ng syempre ng meeting sa meeting then sa mga program didto ko sila ma kilalala pagid dayon duw maka reach out man saila kay ng kung kis a abi duw ako ang ma huya then kung kis a abi duw di abi ko nila makita nga ng as in officer na mas ano pa saila duw ng gina barkada barkada nila ko duw maano man ko saila nga ga getting to know. (P3/67-71-Rosemarie)

(In all meetings and programs, I can acknowledge them and can reach out to them since there are times that I am shy and they cannot see me as an officer. They started to be close to me, and we know each other.)

Rosemarie also shared her idea that they allow exemptions for other members who cannot attend their meetings.

Kung kis a about sa online nga ano nang gina pa ano namon sila nang kung kis a nang exemptions nalang gid, kay daw wala nalng sila gina ano, kay di man sila piliton abi. (P3/105-107-Rosemarie)

(Sometimes, when we are online, we provide exemptions since we cannot force them.)

➤ *Following the Courtesy Call*

Lastly, student leaders are guided by different principles. Even though they are in difficult times, they manage to be courteous toward other people. That indicates that they possess a good character as a good role model, especially to the younger generations and to the other students. Melvin shared his insight on how he reasonably treats others.

So una una gid sina syempre mag lisensya gid kami sang tarong kalain man nga mag rason kami sang iban iban. (P4/80-81-Nielvin)

(So, the first thing is that we need to ask permission because it is not suitable if we reason out something which is not valid.)

C. *What personal developments gained by the student leaders in overcoming their leadership difficulties?*

Table 3: presents the personal developments gained in overcoming the difficulties.

Emergent Themes	Clustered Themes
Expansion of Knowledge	Able to gain the necessary knowledge for practical application in the future. Acquire relevant skills such as legal writing and making reports.
Maximizing Leadership Potentials	Develop the boldness to express one's opinion. Acquired the needed leadership skills for future application and use. Enhanced Self Confidence. Developed Matured Mindset as a Leader. Able to acquire other skills in leadership not taught in the classroom. Learned how to socialize and interact with others appropriately. Learned how to fulfil duties with efficiency properly. Trained to be more responsible with priorities. Able to manage time and tasks appropriately. Became a better leader.
Strengthening the Social Connections	Be able to establish confidence in interacting with other officers and members. Learned to show and impart talents to others and the organization. Became more responsible with commitments and in dealing with others.

➤ *Expansion of Knowledge*

As student leaders engage in leadership, they can easily absorb the learnings given by the experiences and the fact that they are allowed to grow. Student leaders can improve themselves and their abilities as they explore more and innovate ways to cope with the tasks being given to them. Michelle said she needs the experience since those experiences will be helpful enough when she encounters different trials or difficulties. As such, when she creates paper works, it will help her improve her writing skills.

Kailangan ko man sya kay kailangan ko sang experience kay halimbawa mag himo kami mga papers ma guidedan gid kami sang amun nga mga advisers kag

*para may ara naman bala ko sang knowledge para magamit ko para sa future.
(P1/67-70-Michelle)*

(I need it since I need experience. For example, when we create paper works, we are guided by our advisers for them to have prior knowledge, which I can apply in the future.)

Every student leader has the capacity and abilities that are useful enough in their endeavour as a leader. They are allowed to showcase their abilities, and in that way, they can learn more and learn something about it. Joining the organization will be one of the most effective ways to expand their knowledge and discover more about their roles. Student leaders have been given a different task to do, which includes paper works. So, Melvin shared his insight on what skills he has gained as he enters the life of being a student leader.

Literary skills kay syempre naga try ka man sang mga reports mo, so amo gid na ang mga makuha mo nga skills. (P4/134-135-Nielvin)

(Literary skills since you are trying to create your reports. That is the skill that you can get.)

➤ *Maximizing Leadership Potentials*

Engaging in student leadership will be a platform to widen the understanding of life and to improve skills in all aspects of life. As a student leader, it is a greater responsibility to voice opinions freely and express ideas about something. Some considerable skills and benefits can be gained by engaging in student leadership. Those shy type leaders will boost their self-confidence and develop the ability to be true leaders to speak in front of the different faces of the students. Robert as a participant has given different insights on how he develops himself as a true leader. Those skills have a unique purpose and will be lifelong skills applicable shortly.

Damo damo gid ko may nakuha just how to become a leader but ma apply gid sya in real life kag ma apply mo gid sya uhh kumbaga indi sya nga asta lang dira kumbaga nang anu kumbaga lifelong sya kumbaga asta mag tanda ta pwede ta sya madala nga mga anu. (P2/98-101-Robert)

(We can gain a lot, not just on how to become a leader, but it is applicable in real life, if we are old, we can use it.)

Additionally, Robert also shared that engaging in student leadership helps boost self-confidence, especially when speaking and delivering a speech in front of.

Uhhh siguro uhhh hindi man sa anu pero mas na boost ang confidence ko kumbaga wala na ko huya sometimes I am giving my speech or message sa mga programs makaya ko na bisan wala na sang mga script bisan on the spot makaya ko na sya. (P2/107-110-Robert)

(It boosts my confidence. Now, I am not shy anymore when I deliver my speech or message in every program. I can deliver it without a script, and even on the spot, I can manage to do it.)

In addition, Robert also shared that engaging student leadership can be a platform for a mature mindset, and there is room for the student leader to their personality.

For me indi lang na sya sang kumbaga parang there are room for improvement for that kumbaga habang ga dugay nga ga dugay ga improve kag ga mature pud ang pagiging leadership or pagiging leader ko. (P2/111-113-Robert)

(For me, there is room for improvement for that. As time passes, I am improving and maturing as a leader.)

Robert gave the idea that many skills can be gained in engaging in student leadership and can be helpful enough to create different papers works.

Then parang siguro sa skills sobrang dami na mga like na masabi ko nga ang mga wala gina tudlo sang adviser namun sa classroom or sang mga teachers like creating activity designs, resolutions how to conduct parliamentary mga ganyan na bagay kumbaga sa SSG ko lang gid natun-an kag uhh indi na sya matun-an sa classroom pero depende na sya sa topic siguro or sa subject. (P2/114-119-Robert)

(In terms with the skills, there are a lot. I can say that those things that our teacher cannot teach us in our classroom like creating activity design and resolutions how to conduct parliamentary, I can learn it through the SSG. It cannot be learned in a classroom but it depends to the topic or the subject.)

One of the main characteristics of a leader is to have strong self-confidence, especially when facing different personalities and students. They have the confidence to voice opinions towards a specific topic or problem. Engaging in SSG will be an excellent platform to overcome the fear of facing other people. Michelle and Rosemarie explained their experiences in how the two of them developed strong self-confidence and the freedom to voice their opinions.

Well, dako gid ang mabulig nya kuya kay nang ma voice out namun ang amun nga mga opinion then sa personality like sa gin hambal ko kagina nga ma voice ko gid ang akon mga opinions dati abi nang mga opinions gd ko since wala ko sa position daw budlay kay basi di ka nila pamatian pero sine nga naging VP nako daw na improve sya. (P1/86-90-Michelle)

(Well, it is a huge help since we can voice our opinions rather than our personality. As I said earlier, we could voice our opinions. In the past, it was hard for me to share my opinions because of the tendency of not being heard, and now that I am VP, it was improved.)

Moreover, Rosemarie had the same idea that self-confidence was one of the things that developed in her personality when she started to engage herself in student leadership.

So, tung dati tung ano gid man ng mahuya gid ko sa ano, pero subong daw may confidence na bala nga ano mag kwan sa ila, tapos makipag halubilo. Kay dati gid abi ng nd gid ko palaestorya sa iban bala haw. So, ang self-confidence amo na ang nag boost sa akon. (P3/112-115-Rosemarie)

(So, in the past, I am shy, but now I have the confidence to interact with them and engage since in the past, I am not talkative with the concerns of other people. So, my self-confidence is boosted.)

In addition, many skills are being improved in engaging in the world of leadership and equipped with different knowledge, which will help a lot in different aspects of life. One participant has said that there are lots of things that can be learned in SSG, like how to handle or budget funds, and the most crucial part is the development of time management. Since time is significant for a leader, the fact that a student leader faces many responsibilities and time management should be prioritized. Melvin and Rosemarie have shared their insight towards time management and the skills that can be learned as a student leader.

Nan, amo pa gid na kuya kay ng damo gid ko natun an sa pag budget sa kwarta, sa pag paano ko sya eh ilistahon kung paano gid bala ng pasikotsikot bala haw. Daw hala amo nalang alang na bilin na kwarta bala haw, so dapat listahon ko na tanan nga gin pang kuha namon mga expenses namon, amo pagid na ang ano sa akon pagiging treasurer. (P3/123-127-Rosemarie)

(I have learned a lot about how to budget money, how I will make a list and the other ways. If I only have less money left, all of our expenses should be listed; that is the thing for me as a treasurer.)

On the other hand, Rosemarie also shared that doing different works in their organization will make it a lifestyle, especially time management.

Then mahimo mo na sya nga lifestyle mo nga mag ano sa imo nga time management. (P3/150-151-Rosemarie)

(Then it will make a lifestyle to have time management.)

Moreover, Nielvin also highlighted that leadership skills and time management could be observed as one of the personal developments that developed in his personality.

So sang nag sali ko sa SSG, so ang akon gid nga una nga personal development nga natabo sa akon is time management, syempre kay double work ka man, may academics kapa maliban sa academics may ara kapa hirimuon sa balay nyu, may ara kapa sa SSG activities. (P4/106-109-Nielvin)

(So, when I entered SSG, the first personal development that happened to me was time management because of the double work, academics, household chores and SSG activities.)

In addition, Melvin also shared that leadership skills are the skill that develops the most. Just like in handling the lower officers.

Leadership sya, leadership skills gid ang maka improve sa amon kay may gina handle man kami nga mga lower SSG officers nga iban. (P4/128-129-Nielvin)

(Leadership skills improved us personally since we are handling other lower SSG officers.)

➤ *Strengthening the Social Connections*

As a student leader establishing a good relationship with the people around them should be maintained. They know how to communicate effectively and establish a solid personality to perform their responsibilities. Engaging in student leadership has many benefits, which help build a bridge towards other people. It will create an excellent environment to maintain harmony at school. Participants can express their experiences and the changes they feel when they enter the field of leadership. Michelle shared her insight on strengthening her social connections, especially with fellow students and officers.

Since VP ko o kailangan ko gid na I anu, kag amu pa gd na dati kuya indi gid ko mahilig mag isturya or something sa mga anu, So since nag join Ko kag VP ang akon nga position so kailangan ko gd mag interact sa akon mga Officers kag sa iban pa gd nga mga students lalo na gid sa mga presidents sang mga classroom kay kis a abi nabudlayan man sila sa mga classmates nila lalo na ang mga grade 7 kay indi pa sila kilalahay gina buligan man namun sila so amu mana nag bulig sa akon para maka interact man ko kag na anu ko man ang personality. (P1/72-79-Michelle)

(Since I am VP, I need that. Another thing from the past years, I am not fond of talking. So, since I joined, the VP has been my position. Hence, I need to interact with other officers and the other students, especially the presidents of each classroom, since there are times that they struggle with their classmates, especially the Grade 7. They are not familiar with each other. So we help them and in that way, it can also help me with my personality.)

Through the activities being held by the student leaders, they can create unity among themselves and the other students. Moreover, Robert and Rosemarie also shared their point of view on how student leaders interact when they have activities being held at school.

Like for example sa teamwork pud sa unity and then sa mga skills although kay hindi man sa mga most of the student leaders syempre nang hindi na nga ano pero dapat may skills pud ta maybe indi sa iban na anu pero I truly believe na ano tanan ta may skills pero need ta lang gid sya ipakita kag siguro amuna ang isa sa mga bagay nga kumbaga like for example like other student leaders namun like dati wala sila ga saot pero subong ma develop gid nila kay syempre maka saot gid sila sa ano. (P2/126-132-Robert)

(Like for example, teamwork, unity and skills. Although most of the student leaders do not have skills. Maybe not to other things but I genuinely believe that all of us have skills, we need to showcase them. In the beginning, student leaders are not fond of dancing. Now, they improved since they can dance now.)

Rosemarie also expressed her idea that in engaging with student leadership, they can socialize with other people and be responsible for their responsibilities at school.

Ng sa pagiging responsible man na SSG officer nga makipaghalubilo man kag mag estorya sa mga teachers, kag maging responsible man sa akong duties as an officer kag sa modules ko. (P3/117-119-Rosemarie)

(To be responsible as an SSG officer and know how to socialize and communicate with the teachers. We have to be responsible for the duties of an officer and my modules.)

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the summary of the experiences of the participants, important insights, and implications based on the insights drawn in the study.

A. Difficulties of the student leaders in facing the new normal.

This study collected different insights, especially the leadership difficulties of the student leaders. Since we are currently facing the changes of the new normal, most student leaders encounter difficulties along with their leadership journey. Student leaders may lose their interest and courage to attend important gatherings and meetings. Most of them are unavailable since the setup is limited and most of their meetings are held online.

Another point is that student leaders encounter communication barriers. They shared that most of the student leaders encounter connectivity issues and the availability of internet connections. Moreover, due to these reasons, student leaders face difficulties in disseminating important information and reaching the other officers. In connection to that matter, it resulted in the situation wherein most of the student leaders cannot participate and they face difficulty in conducting their meetings.

Furthermore, since the pandemic has greatly affected all aspects of life one of the difficulties being encountered by the student leaders is the financial inadequacy and then inadequacy of budget for their organization. The goal of student leaders is to provide services to their fellow students but these days, they encounter difficulty in finding the source of funds due to the limitation brought by the new normal. They find it challenging since they are facing a shortage of funds to raise and support their plans. Up until now, student leaders face hurdles in the implementation of their plans and services in a way that they find it difficult to sustain their programs, and at the same time, they cannot freely implement their plans because the mode of education, for now, is held through online. Another thing is that since the role of being a student leader is complex they also explained that they are loaded with different tasks which include their academics, household chores, and their responsibilities to the organization.

Lastly, since the pandemic has evolved and the student leaders encountered pandemic-related obstacles, they find it hard to deal with it and adjust to the new normal setting. Another point to consider is that student leaders are prohibited and restricted by their parents since their parents are threatened by the threats of pandemic which includes the health of their children. So according to the student leaders, they are being prohibited to go out by their parents.

B. Ways of the student leaders in overcoming those difficulties.

The study revealed that student leaders encountered different difficulties in facing the new normal. So, in connection to this, the study also identified the ways being undertaken by the student leaders in overcoming those difficulties. The participants freely shared their actions being done to overcome the difficulties they encounter in facing the new normal setting.

One of the given ways the participant is being connected is since the normal ways of life were being changed by the new normal the student leaders need to be connected. They ensure that all of their announcements and reminders are being disseminated and at the same time, they are connected with their major officers. One of the easier ways for them to connect with other student leaders is to conduct online meetings to disseminate important information.

Furthermore, the shortage of funds is one of their difficulties so the student leaders maximize their alternatives to generate funds just like soliciting funds from other people. In that way, they can raise funds to support their plans and activities. Student leaders also conduct house-to-house visitations so that they can monitor the conditions of the other student leaders. At some point, student leaders had given too many responsibilities to be done, and most of them shared that they keep on looking at the positive side of life and they take a breather if they are exhausted with their tasks.

Lastly, one of the most interesting parts that the student leaders shared is that they are being courteous in dealing with the restrictions of their parents. Even though they have different tasks to be prioritized they choose to obey and respect the order of their parents. Moreover, they also establish good relationships with other student leaders.

C. Personal developments gained by the student leaders in overcoming those difficulties.

Student leaders had faced different difficulties in their leadership journey and in line with that student leaders undertake different ways to overcome those difficulties. In that way, student leaders shared their personal developments as they overcame those leadership difficulties.

Student leaders shared that when they joined as student leaders they had the opportunity to expand their knowledge. As they acquire different skills which are useful enough in their future endeavors. They can also maximize their knowledge about the different paper works and how they manage their financial matters to support their organization. It is also one of the things that they highlighted that as a student leader, it is important to establish proper time management to organize the things that need to be done.

In addition, student leaders also express their idea that through student leadership they can able to maximize their leadership potential in a way that they can acquire the needed leadership skills for future purposes. It includes establishing self-confidence to express their opinions on a certain matter. They can freely share their insight without hesitations and face numerous people to present something. Student leaders also become better leaders as they learn how to fulfill their duties properly and are trained to choose their priorities. Furthermore, as student leaders, they have developed a mature mindset especially when they are in a difficult situation and they can produce better decisions.

Lastly, they shared that they are able to strengthen their social connections as they establish confidence when they interact with other people that surround them. They became more responsible with their commitments and at the same time learned to show and impart talents to others and the organization.

D. Implication for Practice

The main aim of this study was to explore and understand the leadership experiences of student leaders in facing the new normal. As the participants undergo the interview process they respond to the questions being given to them and it reflects their difficulties in their duties as student leaders. Another thing is that they also provided the ways on how they overcome those difficulties and the personal developments they gained in overcoming those difficulties.

Based on the significant results as seen in the participant's responses, all of them shared their firsthand experiences, especially their leadership experiences. During the time of pandemic, they experienced a lot of difficulties such as disinterest and apathy, communication barriers, and financial inadequacy. Another response had been gathered as they encountered pandemic-related obstacles, hurdles in the implementation and delivery of their services, and also to their tasks and parental prohibitions.

In this sense, the researcher believed that this study is timely amid the new normal, as it answers the difficulties of the student leaders, their ways, and the personal developments they have gained in overcoming those difficulties. This means that this study is useful enough to provide solutions to the leadership difficulties being encountered by student leaders and how they provide possible solutions to them.

The implication of this study is to help student leaders to overcome their leadership difficulties. As the study presents different experiences being encountered by the student leaders it will serve as a guide for the student leaders to have an overview of how student leaders deal with their leadership journey as they face new normal changes. This study suggests that student leaders must learn to adjust and have a positive mindset toward their roles as student leaders. They must learn to maximize alternative ways for them to progress to the tasks being given to them.

In addition, this study implies that all student leaders must allow having better plans to cope with the demand of the new normal. Since student leadership is one of the effective platforms for student leaders to expand their knowledge, maximize their leadership potential and most important thing is to strengthen their social connection with the people around them.

Lastly, this study implies that teachers and parents should allow student leaders to have the freedom to do the things they wanted to discover. As student leadership is the right path for the student leaders to build their self confidence and their personality so that they can express their insights and opinions without hesitation and fear.

E. Implications for Future Research

This Qualitative Study dealt with student leader's experiences in facing the new normal. Considering the results and the processes that this study had gone through, it implied that:

Based on the findings of this study, future researchers who are interested in investigating the study's findings must look into a more specific selection of participants, taking into account their academic achievements and their conditions, as this may lead to interesting comparisons from the current study.

Furthermore, this study also suggests that family members, instructors, classmates, acquaintances, and other people with whom the participant interacts be interviewed. The information they provide can help future researchers gain a better understanding of how student leaders manage their difficulties in their roles as student leaders.

This study also suggests that public high school administrators create a program to assist and encourage their student leaders. Furthermore, the government, particularly the Department of Education (DepEd), must develop a program to assist student leaders, such as leadership training, and financial support, particularly for those studying in public high school, and hold a seminar on time management for student leaders.

F. Concluding Remarks

This study was made with the full determination and perseverance of the researcher. The researcher gives a huge amount of time to accomplish this important study. The whole journey and experiences in writing all the parts of the paper had a huge impact and realization on the researcher's life. The sleepless nights, mental breakdowns, and financial matters are one of the main hindrances in creating this study. Since the researcher is fully determined to work and finish the study despite the problems being encountered he successfully developed and created this research study. The struggles are always there but the researcher uses this research as a goal to achieve his goals in life.

In addition, without the support of the people around the researcher, it will be hard to manage those trials. The researcher wants to share that doing research is one of the toughest and most challenging parts of the life of a college student. It needs prior knowledge, mental health discipline, financial support and to have time management. Creating these pieces of paper is considered a test of how the researcher will survive and create ways how to survive this kind of matter. Creating this kind of study is quite meaningful as it helps the students to have a broader understanding of the present situation. This study will also serve as evidence of the patience of the researcher as he further discovers the life of the student leaders and finds meaningful stories about their leadership journey.

Since the main aim of this study is to explain the leadership difficulties being encountered by student leaders, especially in our time today, we are currently facing the changes being brought by the new normal. The participants of this study firmly agreed that being a student leader will provide different skills which are helpful in the future. Thus, the participants also expressed their experiences which include their difficulties in facing the changes brought by the new normal. According to the responses, participants were able to maximize their leadership potential, expand their knowledge, and strengthen their social connections. This study will be a tool to enlighten the student leaders who encounter trials in managing their trials as student leaders. Moreover, the personal developments being given by the participants will serve as motivation to other students so that they will have an interest to join student leadership.

Lastly, the life of student leaders is inevitably quite challenging as they face different trials and they need to be responsible in managing their time towards their roles. This study will enlighten the readers, future researchers, and parents about the important role of a student leader, especially in how they deal with the difficulties that come to their lives.

INTERVIEW MATRIX

RQ NO. 1 - What are the difficulties encountered by student leaders during their leadership journey?			
kung mag held kami sang meeting namun indi available ang tanan.	P1/35-Michelle	Non-participation of members during meetings or assembly;	DISINTEREST AND APATHY
well communication gid ang main problem subong,	P1/26-Michelle	Lack of communication among members;	COMMUNICATION BARRIER
26 .then sa budget Man namun indi abi kami maka pangita sang budget subong	P1/26-27-Michelle	Inadequacy of budget for the organization;	FINANCIAL INADEQUACY
Kung mag interact kami dire sa school may ara gid sang indi sang sugtan lalo na Tung mga indi pa fully vaccinated.	P1/45-46-Michelle	Limitations in the activities due to health protocol;	Inadequacy of budget for the organization
Like subong na year kuya, ano abi kay budlay abi sya subong na Year na mag anu kami sang rules kuya kay indi sya face to face classes.	P1/16-17-Michelle	Enactment of rules is difficult due to social distancing and health protocols;	PANDEMIC-RELATED OBSTACLES
Interviewee: siguro first and foremost syempre to conduct programs projects and activities specifically mga programs na gusto namon I sustain like under the project na palayok that project started sa time ni kuya Leo until now gina sustain sya for sustainability.	P2/19-22-Robert	Difficulty in conducting ang sustaining programs;	HURDLES IN IMPLEMENTATION AND SERVICE DELIVERY
kung may online activity for all kasi ang possible na face to face is mga selected students lang gd pero kung for all students gd syempre naga struggle kami kay syempre sa officer namon di tanan magkaroon ng internet connection like sometimes di tanan maka join like sometimes mag conduct kami sang meetings	P2/32-35-Robert	Difficulty to conduct meetings due to connectivity problems;	COMMUNICATION BARRIER
48.example may ara activities last time and supposed to be tapuson ko pa ang mga 49. requirements ko so parang anu lang man gina control lang man nga basi ma 50. Sobrahan	P2/48-50-Robert	Loaded with requirements to comply and submit;	A PILE-LOAD OF TASKS
Syempre budlay gid subong actually until now naga adjust pa kami sa what we call this sa new normal nga set up	P2/59-60-Robert	Adjustment complexities brought by the new normal;	PANDEMIC-RELATED OBSTACLES
maybe ano lang sa participants lang kay gamay lang na pwede ang	P2/25-27-Robert	Difficulty in gathering participants;	DISINTEREST AND APATHY

participants na ma kuha namon pero in conducting subong hindi na sya kayo budlay unlike dati.			
86.there are sometimes nga 87.madulaan na matak-an na madulaan na gana	P2/86-87- Robert	Loss of interest among members;	DISINTEREST AND APATHY
17.Interviewee: Uhhh first kay syempre kay pandemic subong ang perti gid ka budlay is ang pag organize sang mga ano sang classroom	P3/17-18- Rosemarie	Difficulty with Classroom organization;	HURDLES IN IMPLEMENTAT ION AND SERVICE DELIVERY
18.paano mag 19. implement gd sang imo mga bag o nga principles or mga rules	P3/18-19- Rosemarie	Problems with Implementation of rules;	HURDLES IN IMPLEMENTAT ION AND SERVICE DELIVERY
So ng isa pagid kay ng hindi face to face na makitanay ang mga ano ang iban nga mga officers nga under sa amon nang hindi sila kaayo ga participate kay isa pa gid indi pa gid sila namon makita kag indi namon maakigan man so far amu man lang na.	P3/19-22- Rosemarie	Non-participation of members in the activities conducted;	DISINTEREST AND APATHY
27.Kung para lang sa akon ang first nga indi gid sila pag sugtan kay 28. syempre pandemic so ang iban abi nga parents nila nang strict bala haw	P3/27-28- Rosemarie	Parents do not give their consent to their children;	PARENTAL PROHIBITIONS
46.ahh ng ano ahh mas nabudlayan ko subong ang mag ano man mag 47. reach out sa iban nga officers.	P3/46-47- Rosemarie	Problem in reaching out the other officers;	COMMUNICATI ON BARRIER
May ara man kuy ng sa internet connection then sa iban ng sa time nila kay ang iban indi man ka attend gid kay indi available kay wla sila load so pero madayun gid gyapon kay more than man kami sa meeting.	P3/79-81- Rosemarie	Some officers could not participate because they do not have internet connection;	COMMUNICATI ON BARRIER
Ahh subong nga may pandemic, number one gid nga problem nga Ma encounter namun is lack of communication gid sya kay especially kung mag Pa meeting kami ang iban sa amun is lagyo	P4/18-20- Nielvin	Lack of communication due to connectivity issues;	COMMUNICATI ON BARRIER
20.daw budlay maka communicate kag mabudlay ma relay ang mga info. Nga halin sa itaas	P4/20-21- Nielvin	Difficulty in Disseminating or relaying Information;	COMMUNICATI ON BARRIER
24.Ah maliban sina is syempre kay iban indi man sugtan kay tungod sa	P4/24-27- Nielvin	Parental Limitations and not giving of	PARENTAL PROHIBITIONS

25.Pandemic indi man sugtan nga mag gwa or indi sugtan sang parents nila so 26.Isa gid na sya sa problems namun kay indi namun kumbaga indi namun makaya 27. Ang isa ka activity kung kulang kami.		consent;	
Oomm isa gid na sya sa mga problema namun so kay biskan mag Meeting kmi daw ang iban daw ma intindihan man pero kay chappy sya indi gid Sya ma anu maayu.	P4/31-33- Nielvin	Unsteady or intermittent Internet Connections;	COMMUNICATI ON BARRIER
May ara kami sang activity sa academic nga daw indi namun ma supalpalan Tanan kaya daw ga conflict gid sya so maka pili gid kami kung anu ang priority Namun although nga amu sina ang amun nga mga teacher	P4/45-47- Nielvin	Conflicts with other equally important activities;	A PILE-LOAD OF TASKS

RQ NO. 2 - In what ways do the student leaders undertake to overcome their leadership difficulties?

51.Well naga communicate nalang kami nga mga major officers	P1/51- Michelle	Communicate with other major officers;	STAYING CONNECTED
55.Kag kung kis naga house to house kami.	P1/55- Michelle	Look for other ways such as House Visitation;	MAXIMIZING ALTERNATIVES
59. announcement lang kung may mag lakat sa school like ligad dire may meeting	P1/59-61- Michelle	Make updates or leave Announcements;	MAXIMIZING ALTERNATIVES
18.Mga anu nalang naga conduct nalang kami sang mga activities then naga hold 19.Kami sang mga Gmeet. Then Gina Contact nalang namun ang mga president 20.Each room.	P1/18-20- Michelle	Conduct Online Meetings or inform class presidents;	STAYING CONNECTED
27.Man namun indi abi kami maka pangita sang budget subong pero last time sang 28.December didtu lang kmi naka kuha sang dako na budget kay naka solicit	P1/27-28- Michelle	Solicit funds and generate income through initiatives;	REACHING OUT TO OTHERS

kami. 29. In a way nga nag caroling kami.			
73. uhh internet naman subong mostly so why not lets maximize the use of social 74. media so naga conduct kami sang mga activities through online not just in 75. facebook but we are extending our social media just like instagram twitter and 76. then uhhh naga use din kami nang zoom or google meet for us to conduct 77. activities together virtually.	P2/73-77- Robert	Utilize other forms of social media to maximize communication and participation;	MAXIMIZING ALTERNATIVES
80. Interviewee: Simple lang nga mga steps, siguro first and foremost to motivate 81. myself because at the end of the day I cannot motivate or lead a certain group or 82. this school or group of student leaders in this school ahh without motivating my 83. self	P2/80-83- Robert	Be optimistic and motivate oneself despite the challenges;	LOOKING INTO POSITIVITY
87. uhhh anu lang siguro take 88. rest after take a rest balik naman liwat.	P2/87-88- Robert	Find time to rest or relax;	TAKING A BREATHER
67. ng syempre ng meeting sa meeting then sa mga program didto ko 68. sila ma kilalala pagid dayon duw maka reach out man saila kay ng kung kis a abi 69. duw ako ang ma huya then kung kis a abi duw di abi ko nila makita nga ng as in 70. officer na mas ano pa saila duw ng gina barkada barkada nila ko duw maano 71. man ko saila nga ga getting to know.	P3/67-71- Rosemarie	Establish better relationship with members or co-officers;	WEARING ANOTHER'S SHOES
105. Kung kis a about sa online nga ano nang gina pa ano namon sila 106. nang kung kis a nang exemptions nalang gid, kay daw wala nalng sila gina ano, 107. kay di man sila piliton abi	P3/105-107- Rosemarie	Understand the situation of others by exempting them from the activities;	WEARING ANOTHER'S SHOES
76. So ang gina himo namon sina is, una palang daw gina pa balo na 77. namon una palang para maka prepare ang mga iban nga officers.	P4/76-77- Nielvin	Ensure information update and make constant reminders;	STAYING CONNECTED
80. So una una gid sina syempre mag	P4/80-81-	Asking	FOLLOWING

lisensya gid kami sang tarong 81. kalain man nga mag rason kami sang iban iban.	Nielvin	Permissions and consent properly to the administration or concerned persons;	THE COURTESY CALL
96. So ang gina himo namon dira is, daw gina encourage nalang 97. sila namon pero ang pag encourage namun is in different way nang gina send 98. namon kung ano kami ka happy sa mga activity nga gina himo namon samtang 99. kami naga work as student leaders	P4/96-99- Nielvin	Encourage the members about the purpose and result of the activity;	LOOKING INTO POSITIVITY

RQ NO. 3 - What were the personal developments gained by the student leaders in overcoming their leadership difficulties?			
67. kailangan ko man sya kay kailangan 68. ko sang experience kay halimbawa mag himo kami mga papers ma guidedan gid 69. kami sang amun nga mga advicers kag para may ara naman bala ko sang 70. knowledge para magamit ko para sa future.	P1/67-70- Michelle	Able to gain important knowledge for practical application in the future;	EXPANSION OF KNOWLEDGE
86. sInterviewee: Well dako gid ang mabulig nya kuya kay nang ma voice out namun 87. ang amun nga mga opinion then sa personality like sa gin hambal ko kagina nga 88. ma voice ko gid ang akon mga opinions dati abi nang mga opinions gd ko since 89. wala ko sa position daw budlay kay basi di ka nila pamatian pero sine nga naging 90. VP nako daw na improve sya.	P1/86-90- Michelle	Develop the boldness to express one's opinion;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
72. Interviewee: Since VP ko o kailangan ko gid na I anu, kag amu pa gd na dati 73. kuya indi gid ko mahilig mag isturya or something sa mga anu, So since nag join 74. Ko kag VP ang akon nga position so kailangan ko gd mag interact sa akon mga 75. Officers kag sa iban pa gd nga mga students lalo na gid sa mga presidents sang 76. mga classroom kay kis a abi nabudlayan man sila sa mga classmates nila lalo na 77. ang mga grade 7 kay indi pa sila kilalahay gina buligan man namun silaso amu	P1/72-79- Michelle	Be able to establish confidence in interacting with other officers and members;	STRENGTHENING THE SOCIAL CONNECTIONS

78. mana nag bulig sa akon para maka interact man ko kag na anu ko man ang 79. personality.			
98. damo damo gid ko may nakuha just how to become a leader but ma apply gid 99. sya in real life kag ma apply mo gid sya uhh kumbaga indi sya nga asta lang dira 100. kumbaga nang anu kumbaga lifelong sya kumbaga asta mag tanda ta pwede ta 101. sya madala nga mga anu.	P2/98-101- Robert	Acquired the needed leadership skills for future application and use;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
107. Interviewee: Uhhh siguro uhhh hindi man sa anu pero mas na boost ang 108. confidence ko kumbaga wala na ko huya sometimes I am giving my speech or 109. message sa mga programs makaya ko na bisan wala na sang mga script bisan 110. on the spot makaya ko na sya	P2/107-110- Robert	Enhanced Self Confidence;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
111. for me indi lang na sya sang kumbaga parang there are room for improvement 112. for that kumbaga habang ga dugay nga ga dugay ga improve kag ga mature 113. pud ang pagiging leadership or pagiging leader ko	P2/111-113- Robert	Developed Matured Mindset as a Leader;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
114. then parang siguro sa 115. skills sobrang dami na mga like na masabi ko nga ang mga wala gina tudlo 116. sang adviser namun sa classroom or sang mga teachers like creating activity 117. designs, resolutions how to conduct parliamentary mga ganyan na bagay 118. kumbaga sa SSG ko lang gid natun-an kag uhh indi na sya matun-an sa 119. classroom pero depende na sya sa topic siguro or sa subject.	P2/114-119- Robert	Able to acquire other skills in leadership not taught in the classroom;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
126. like for example sa teamwork pud sa unity and then sa mga skills although kay 127. hindi man sa mga most of the student leaders syempre nang hindi na nga ano 128. pero dapat may skills pud ta maybe indi sa iban na anu pero I trully believe na 129. ano tanan ta may skills pero need ta lang gid sya ipakita kag siguro amuna ang 130. isa sa mga bagay nga kumbaga like for example like other student leaders 131. namun like dati wala sila ga saot pero subong ma develop gid nila kay syempre 132. maka saot gid sila sa ano.	P2/126-132- Robert	Learned to show and impart talents for others and the organization;	STRENGTHENING THE SOCIAL CONNECTIONS
112. So, tung dati tung ano gid man ng mahuya gid ko sa ano, pero 113. subong dow may confidence na bala nga	P3/112-115-	Learned how to socialize and interact with	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP

<p>ano mag kwan sa ila, tapos makipag</p> <p>114. halubilo. Kay dati gid abi ng nd gid ko palaestorya sa iban bala haw. So, ang</p> <p>115. self-confidence amo na ang nag boost sa akon.</p>	Rosemarie	others properly;	POTENTIALS
<p>117.Ng sa pagiging responsible man na SSG officer nga</p> <p>118.makipaghalubilo man kag mag estorya sa mga teachers, kag maging</p> <p>119.responsible man sa akong duties as an officer kag sa modules ko.</p>	P3/117-119-Rosemarie	Became more responsible with the commitments and in dealing with others;	STRENGTHENING THE SOCIAL CONNECTION
<p>123. Nan, amo pa gid na kuya kay ng damo gid ko natun an sa pag</p> <p>124. budget sa kwarta, sa pag paano ko sya eh ilistahon kung paano gid bala ng</p> <p>125. pasikotsikot bala haw. Daw hala amo nalang alang na bilin na kwarta bala haw,</p> <p>126. so dapat listahon ko na tanan nga gin pang kuha namon mga expenses namon,</p> <p>127. amo pagid na ang ano sa akon pagiging treasurer.</p>	P3/123-127-Rosemarie	Learned how to properly fulfil duties with efficiency;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
<p>150. then mahimo mo na sya nga lifestyle mo nga mag ano</p> <p>151. sa imo nga time management.</p>	P3/150-151-Rosemarie	Trained to be more responsible with priorities;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
<p>106. So sang nag sali ko sa SSG, so ang akon gid nga una nga</p> <p>107. personal development nga natabo sa akon is time management, syempre kay</p> <p>108. double work ka man, may academics kapa maliban sa academics may ara kapa</p> <p>109. hirimuon sa balay nyu, may ara kapa sa SSG activities.</p>	P4/106-109-Nielvin	Able to manage time and tasks properly;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
<p>128. leadership sya, leadership skills gid ang maka improve sa amon kay may gina</p> <p>129. handle man kami nga mga lower SSG officers nga iban.</p>	P4/128-129-Nielvin	Became a better leader;	MAXIMIZING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS
<p>134.literary skills kay syempre naga try ka man sang mga reports mo, so amo gid na</p> <p>135.ang mga makuha mo nga skills.</p>	P4/134-135-Nielvin	Acquire relevant skills such as in legal writing and making reports;	EXPANSION OF KNOWLEDGE

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adams, C., & Gaetane, J. (2011). A diffusion approach to study leadership reform. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 49(4), 354–377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578231111146452>
- [2.] Al-Dabbagh. (2020). The role of decision-maker in crisis ... - wiley online library. The role of decision-maker in crisis. Retrieved March 18, 2022, from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pa.2186>
- [3.] Bosire, J. et. al. (2013). Student leadership in selected public universities in Kenya: Disfranchised pressure groups or an integral component in university management? *African Research Review*. Retrieved March 25, 2022, from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/afrrrev/article/view/41068>
- [4.] Cheon, & Reeve. (2015). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory. Retrieved March 16, 2022, from https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/wpcontent/uploads/2020/04/2020_RyanDeci_CEP_PrePrint.pdf
- [5.] Cress, et. al. (2015). Developmental outcomes of college students' involvement in leadership activities. *Journal of College Student Development*. Retrieved March 18, 2022, from <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2001-16133-002>
- [6.] Creswell, J. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing among Five Approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE. Creswell, J.W. (2013) *Research Design Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 4th edition, Sage Publications, Inc., London. - references - scientific research publishing. Retrieved March 25, 2022, from [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje\)\)/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=1485543](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkposzje))/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=1485543)
- [7.] Colaizzi. (2013). The extension of Colaizzi's method of Phenomenological Enquiry. The extension of Colaizzi's method of phenomenological enquir. Retrieved March 12, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/224887264_The_extension_of_Colaizzi%27s_method_of_phenomenological_enquiry
- [8.] Dugan. (2013). A descriptive analysis of socially responsible leadership. Dugan, J. P. (2013). Involvement and leadership. A descriptive analysis of socially responsible leadership. *Journal of College Student Development*, 47, 335-343. Retrieved March 23, 2022, from <http://www.sciepub.com/reference/39>
- [9.] Eurydice. (2013). *Key data on teachers and school leaders in Europe 2013 Edition*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- [10.] Fiedler, F. E. (2013). A contingency model of Leadership Effectiveness. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*. Retrieved March 23, 2022, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0065260108600519>
- [11.] Gacutan. (2015, February 22). Effectiveness of the performance of the Student Government of North Luzon Philippines State College. *Research in Pedagogy*. Retrieved March 23, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/72177959/Effectiveness_of_the_Performance_of_the_Student_Government_of_North_Luzon_Philippines_State_College
- [12.] Garlejo, S. (2016, February 22). Effectiveness of the performance of the Student Government of North Luzon Philippines State College. *Research in Pedagogy*. Retrieved March 24, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/72177959/Effectiveness_of_the_Performance_of_the_Student_Government_of_North_Luzon_Philippines_State_College
- [13.] Georgis, et. al. (2014). Creating inclusive parent engagement practices: - proquest. Creating inclusive parent engagement practices. Retrieved March 9, 2022, from <https://www.proquest.com/openview/e5eb7d9a15b297a6465552c1720a340d/1?cbl=33246&pq-origsite=gscholar&login=true>
- [14.] Ghergut, A. (2014). Education of children with special needs in Romania; attitudes and ... Retrieved March 15, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257714336_Education_of_Children_with_Special_Needs_in_Romania_Attitudes_and_Experiences

- [15.] Griffiths, F. et.al (2020, August 1). Impact of the societal response to COVID-19 on access to healthcare for non-covid-19 health issues in slum communities of Bangladesh, Kenya, Nigeria and Pakistan: Results of pre-COVID and covid-19 lockdown stakeholder engagements. *BMJ Global Health*. Retrieved March 23, 2022, from <https://gh.bmj.com/content/5/8/e003042.abstract>
- [16.] Hammer. (2013). A literature review of the factors influencing e-learning and ... - ed. *International Journal of Progressive Education*. Retrieved March 15, 2022, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1175336.pdf>
- [17.] Hannah, S. T., et. al. (2014). A framework for examining leadership in extreme contexts. *DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln*. Retrieved March 22, 2022, from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/managementfacpub/39/>
- [18.] Hargreaves, A. (2020). *Collaborative professionalism: When teaching together means learning for all*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
- [19.] Harris, A. (2020). "COVID-19 – School Leadership in Crisis?" *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/2056-9548#earlycite>
- [20.] Harris, A., and M. Jones. (2012). "Connect to Learn: Learn to Connect." *Professional Development Today* 14 (4): 13–19.
- [21.] Isman, A., & Altinay, Z. (2015, September 30). Roles of the students and teachers in distance education. *Online Submission*. Retrieved March 13, 2022, from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED494550>
- [22.] Joseph. (2020, September 17). Research: Women are better leaders during a crisis. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved March 10, 2022, from <https://hbr.org/2020/12/research-women-are-better-leaders-during-a-crisis>
- [23.] Kenny, et.al. (2013). *Conceptualizing educational leadership in an academic development program*. Taylor & Francis. Retrieved March 23, 2022, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1360144X.2019.1570211>
- [24.] Kristin, et. al. (2011). Assessment of Student Leaders' skills critical in managing student affairs in public universities in Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*. Retrieved March 21, 2022, from <http://journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/IJELS/article/view/4910>
- [25.] Komives, et. al. (2014). (PDF) *Leadership Identity Development - Researchgate*. Leadership Identity Development. Retrieved March 10, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273681091_Leadership_Identity_Development
- [26.] Leithwood, K., A. Harris, and D.Hopkins. (2020). "Seven Strong Claims about Successful School Leadership Revisited." *School Leadership & Management* 40 (1): 5–22. doi:10.1080/13632434.2019.1596077.
- [27.] Miles, J. (2010). Leadership development among college-aged students. *E-Journal of Organizational Learning and Leadership*, 8(2): 22-29.
- [28.] Moustakas, C. (2012). *Phenomenological research methods*. American Psychological Association. Retrieved March 10, 2022, from <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1996-97117-000>
- [29.] Mozghan, A., Parivash, J., Nadergholi, G., & Jowkar, B. (2011). Student leadership competencies development. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 1616-1620.
- [30.] Murage, L.M., Njoka, J., Gachahi, M. (2019). Challenges faced by student leaders in managing student affairs in public universities of Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*. Kenya.
- [31.] Mutch, (2014). *the role of schools in Disaster Preparedness, response and recovery: What can we learn from the literature?* Taylor & Francis. Retrieved March 26, 2022, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02643944.2014.880123>
- [32.] Netolicky, D. M. (2020). "School Leadership During a Pandemic: Navigating Tensions." *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/2056-9548#earlycite>
- [33.] Perreault, H., & Waldman, L. (2012, January 10). Overcoming barriers to successful delivery of distance-learning courses. *Journal of Education for Business*. Retrieved March 19, 2022, from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/95609/>

- [34.] Republic of Kenya, & Ojeny, B. (2014, June 19). Kenya Comprehensive School Health Policy: Lessons from a pilot program. *Journal of public health in Africa*. Retrieved March 22, 2022, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5345459/>
- [35.] Roulston. (2010). Considering quality in qualitative interviewing - sage journals. *Considering quality in qualitative interviewing*. Retrieved March 11, 2022, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1468794109356739>
- [36.] Sinem Konuk, M. S. (2021, January). The effectiveness of a student leadership program in Turkey. *The Effectiveness of a Student Leadership Program In Turkey*. Retrieved July 13, 2022, from https://journalofleadershiped.org/wpcontent/uploads/2020/12/20_1_sinukD.pdf
- [37.] Smith, & Riley. (2012). School leadership in times of crisis | request PDF - researchgate. *School leadership in times of crisis*. Retrieved March 11, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233071678_School_leadership_in_times_of_crisis
- [38.] UNICEF. (2013, June 18). Empowered stakeholders: Female University Students' leadership during the COVID-19-triggered on-campus evictions in Canada and the United States - *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*. SpringerLink. Retrieved March 26, 2022, from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13753-021-00362-6>
- [39.] Wingenbach, et.al. (2015). Complexity theory, school leadership and management: Questions for ... Retrieved March 16, 2022, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1741143209359711?journalCode=emad>
- [40.] Yukl, G. (2012). *Leadership in Organizations* (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education. Yukl, G. (2012). *Leadership in organizations* (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ Pearson Education. - References - scientific research publishing. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje\)\)/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=1848184](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnsjt1aadkozje))/reference/referencespapers.aspx?referenceid=1848184)

APPENDIX A

COVER LETTER

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

ALBERT P. BALONGOY, PhD
Vice President of Academic Affair/Adviser
RMMC-MI
Purok Waling- Waling, Arellano Street
Koronadal City, South Cotabato

Sir:

Greeting of peace and prosperity!

I am a third year student taking up Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English enrolled in the subject Methods of Research (Qualitative Research). I would like to ask permission from your office to allow me to conduct an interview to my chosen participants to my study entitled "**LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTIES: A NARRATIVE OF STUDENT LEADERS EXPERIENCES IN FACING THE NEW NORMAL**" within the selected public school in Banga, South Cotabato. This will enable me to know the obstacles they encounter during their leadership journey, what are the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties are and what personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties.

I hope for your favorable response on the matters on hand.

Respectfully yours,

ROGENT LAUDE
Researcher

Approved by:

ALBERT P. BALONGOY, PhD
Adviser/ Vice President of Academic Affair

APPENDIX B

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

INFORMED CONSENT

Dear Participants,

I am a third-year student in Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, Marbel Incorporated pursuing a Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English degree. I'm working on a research entitled " **LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTIES: A NARRATIVE OF STUDENT LEADERS EXPERIENCES IN FACING THE NEW NORMAL** " and I've chosen you to be one of the subjects. The findings of this study will specifically assist me in gathering data based on the interviewer's prepared research questions.

I'd want to hear your stories and personal experiences with student leadership. I want to emphasize that your participation in this study is completely optional, and we will make every attempt to safeguard your identity and keep your information private. I'm excited to hear more about your student leadership experiences and have a better understanding of them. Your involvement will be immensely valued.

Sincerely yours,

ROGEN I. LAUDE
Researcher

APPENDIX C

PARTICIPANTS AGREEMENT FORM

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

PARTICIPANT'S AGREEMENT FORM

I hereby declare that I agree, willing, and understand that my participation in this study entitled **“LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTIES: A NARRATIVE OF STUDENT LEADERS EXPERIENCES IN FACING THE NEW NORMAL”** is an opportunity to share the obstacles I encounter during my leadership journey, what are the ways I undertake to overcome those difficulties and what personal development I have gained in overcoming those difficulties to the Researcher. By signing this, I acknowledge and agree that I read and understand the purpose of the study.

Participants Signature over printed name

Date

APPENDIX D

INTERVIEW GUIDE

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 221 - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

Date:

Place:

Interviewer:

Time Start:

Time End:

Transcriber:

The purpose of this interview and study is to understand the experiences of the student leaders in facing the new normal. . Participants are students in Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges Marbel-Inc. Introduction of myself to the participant. Review the consent form and participants will sign. Review of the questionnaire.

Confidential Questionnaire

Part 1: Warm-up

Name:

Age:

Year:

Gender:

Address:

Part 2: Questions

(S.O.P. Number 1: What are the difficulties they encounter during their leadership journey?)

KAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 221 - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

- What are the difficulties that you have encountered in dealing with your duties and responsibilities as a school leader?

- What do you think are the causes of that challenges?

- How does those challenges affect your daily life?

(S.O.P. Number 2: What are the ways they undertake to overcome those difficulties?)

-What are the usual ways you do in handling those difficulties?

-What are the simple ways that you think helps a lot in dealing with those difficulties?

(S.O.P. Number 3: What personal development they have gained in overcoming those difficulties?)

-How does student leadership help you in developing your personality?

- What are the improvements you have observed when you engage yourself in student leadership?

Prompt Question:

- How can you say that student leadership helps you in improving your personality?

APPENDIX E**TRANSCRIPTION OF DATA**

1. Interviewee Name: Rosemarie B. Ignoro
2. Student Leader From: Banga National High School
3. Position: Treasurer
4. Interviewer: Okay good morning, ng ma start nata sang aton interview for this
5. morning. So ma proceed ko dayon sa aton question number one so uhmm
6. question number one ano gd ang mga diba ahh ano ang position mo subong dire
7. sa SSG?
8. Interviewee: uhmm ng treasurer kuya.
9. Interviewer: treasurer, so since treasurer ka ahh way back sang imo elementary
10. days naging ano karin ba ahh naging elected as SSG officer sang elementary
11. kapa?
12. Interviewee: Ng wala gd kuya pero naga run man ko sa SPG kay ang
13. organization abi SPG kuya.
14. Interviewer: Ayy okay sorry SPG gali. Okay question number one so uhmm ano
15. gd bala ang mga nabudlayan nyo with regards sa inyo mga duties and
16. responsibilities dire sa school sang time subong nga may ara ta sang pandemic?
17. Interviewee: Uhmm first kay syempre kay pandemic subong ang perti gid ka
18. budlay is ang pag organize sang mga ano sang classroom or paano mag
19. implement gd sang imo mga bag o nga principles or mga rules. So ng isa pagid
20. kay ng hindi face to face na makitanay ang mga ano ang iban nga mga officers
21. nga under sa amon nang hindi sila kaayo ga participate kay isa pa gid indi pa gid
22. sila namon makita kag indi namon maakigan man so far amu man lang na.
23. Interviewer: Okay, so diba indi sila maka participate ang iban niyo nga mga co
24. officers diba so I think sa imo ano ang mga rason nga kumbaga indi sila sugtan
25. or nga indi sila maka participate sa inyo mga activities ano ang mga rason sina
26. sa ila kung para lang sa imo.
27. Interviewee: Kung para lang sa akon ang first nga indi gid sila pag sugtan kay
28. syempre pandemic so ang iban abi nga parents nila nang strict bala haw ti isa pa
29. gid kay mga bata pa sila under age pa sila kay representative kay ang iban grade
30. seven, grade 8, grade 9 pero ang iban man maka attend man sila kay nang
31. syempre responsible gd bala sila haw.
32. Interviewer: Diba nabudlayan kamo mag implement sang mga rules and
33. regulations ninyu so how come nga kung paano, ano ang mga ano pa gid ang
34. iban ang mga kumbaga hamlibawa with regards to hamlibawa communication
35. ano wala kamo sang mga problema dira.
36. Interviewee: Ng ma hambal ko subong nga ano kay may ara sa sang mga officer
37. nga ng ano man sa communication so di kaayo sya di man gid kaayo budlay kay
38. ng kay ga participate man pero amo lang gid na may disadvantage man kung kis
39. a kay ang iban hindi man pero more on gid nga duw ma budlayan pero makaya
40. man.
41. Interviewer: Pero kung sa imo personality diin kagid mas na budlayan to perform
42. your duties and responsibilities during this time?
43. Interviewee: Saakon nga personality uhmm hehehe di ko man ma ano oo.
44. Interviewer: Kung diin kagid na budlayan halimbawa sa time management mga
45. amo na sa imo nga sa parents mo.
46. Interviewee: ahh ng ano ahh mas nabudlayan ko subong ang mag ano man mag
47. reach out sa iban nga officers.

48. Interviewer: Ahh oo kung sa parents mo?
49. Interviewee: kung sa parents ko okay lang gid kaayo kay ng bal an man nila nga
50. SSG officer ko kag gusto ko man ti sa time management ko medjo okay ko.
51. Interviewer: Wala kaman nila gina control?
52. Interviewee: wala man.
53. Interviewer: Wala kaman nila gina control so sa imo nga adviser wala kamo
54. problema sainyo mga adviser?
55. Interviewee: Sa adviser ko wala.
56. Interviewer: With regards sa imo nga academics maka affect man sya saimo
57. academics?
58. Interviewee: For me indi gid sya kuya kay may ara bi ko sang schedule ah about
59. sakon modules dayon ng hindi sya maka ano gid duw maka bulig pa sya
60. saakonkay maka gawas ko sa balay dayon maka upod ko sa iban officers maka
61. halubilo ko sa ila
62. Interviewer: Okay, So diba naka mention ka sa ibat iba nga mga problema or
63. mga possible difficulties mo with regards sa imo nga ano tawag na position so
64. kumbaga diba ano ang mga ways mo to overcome those difficulties such as
65. pareho halimbawa satong imo nga atong mag reach out saimo mga co-officers
66. ano mga gina himo ninyo?
67. Interviewee: ng syempre ng meeting sa meeting then sa mga program didto ko
68. sila ma kilalala pagid dayon duw maka reach out man saila kay ng kung kis a abi
69. duw ako ang ma huya then kung kis a abi duw di abi ko nila makita nga ng as in
70. officer na mas ano pa saila duw ng gina barkada barkada nila ko duw maano
71. man ko saila nga ga getting to know.
72. Interviewer: So diba nag hambal ka nga ma huya ka ma consider mo ba nga
73. difficulty mo na ang imo nga personality sa personality mo nga mahuruyaon ka.
74. Interviewee: Oo daw amu na.
75. Interviewer: Ahh ma consider mo man sya gyapon. With regards to conducting
76. your meeting diba naga conduct kamo meeting hambal mo so wla ba kamo dira
77. may ma face nga problema halimbawa sa availability sang mga student ay sa
78. mga co-officers tapos internet connection wla kamo ma problema dira?
79. Interviewee: May ara man kuy ng sa internet connection then sa iban ng sa time
80. nila kay ang iban indi man ka attend gid kay indi available kay wla sila load so
81. pero madayun gid gyapon kay more than man kami sa meeting.
82. Interviewer: Okay so anu pa gid ang iban mo nga way nga gina himo para lang
83. ma overcome nyo to nga problems? Halimbawa sa inyo nman nga parents nga
84. iban nga indi sugtan ano nalang gina himo ninyo?
85. Interviewee: Ng so far subong sa ano kay Robert kay siya gid man abi ang naga
86. anu sina bala haw ng tawag sina ah ng dw gina sugtan lang kay indi mo man abi
87. pwede piliton kag bal an na na nila sa sarili nila nga responsibilidad na na nila
88. nga mag ano sa mga programs kag mag bulig.
89. Interviewer: Diba naga conduct man kamo sang ibat iba nga mga programs wala
90. kamo ano ang imo nga diba syempre diba mahambal mo nga may mga
91. problema man kamo nga gina himo as what have mentioned nila karl nga naga
92. conduct kamo sang mga environmental nga activities so dira wla kamo problema
93. nga ma anu dira kung mag implement kamo?
94. Interviewee: Uhhh subong daw di man gid sya kaayo mahambal mo gid nga
95. problema kay makaya man gyapon.
96. Interviewer: Oo ang pag gather sang participants niyo wla kamo sang problema
97. dira halimbawa mag conduct kamo sang environmental activities maka attend gid
98. bala tanan niyo nga co-officers? Hindi?

99. Interviewee: Indi

100. Interviewer: So uhh during in facing with that kind of problem paano nyo sya

101. kumbaga ma overcome ang uhh kumbaga ano ang gina himo ninyo para ng

102. kumbaga nang maka sali man ang iban diba indi man sila kama sali ti ano ang

103. mga remedy nga gina himo niyo para matagaan nyo sang part tung mga indi

104. man maka attend?

105. Interviewee: Kung kis a about sa online nga ano nang gina pa ano namon sila

106. nang kung kis a nang exemptions nalang gid, kay daw wala nalng sila gina ano,

107. kay di man sila piliton abi.

108. Interviewer: Di ba naka mention ka kagina nga mahuruyaon ka diba? Oo

109. mahuruyaon ka magatubang sa iban nga tao. During nga nag sali ka sa SSG

110. as an officer ano ang mga personal developments mo nga masiling mo nga

111. halimbawa na boost ang self confidence mo? Ano ang mga personal

112. developments mo.

113. Interviewee: So, tung dati tung ano gid man ng mahuya gid ko sa ano, pero

114. subong dow may confidence na bala nga ano mag kwan sa ila, tapos makipag

115. halubilo. Kay dati gid abi ng nd gid ko palaestorya sa iban bala haw. So, ang

116. self-confidence amo na ang nag boost sa akon.

117. Interviewer: Sa mga skills mo?

118. Interviewee: Ng sa pagiging responsible man na SSG officer nga

119. makipaghalubilo man kag mag estorya sa mga teachers, kag maging

120. responsible man sa akong duties as an officer kag sa modules ko.

121. Interviewer:Diba treasurer ka, diba syempre may mga paper works ka eh. Ano

122. ang mga na gain mo nga kumpabaga personal mo gid nga natun-an during mag

123. himo ka sang imo mga nga part as a treasurer.

124. Interviewee: Nan, amo pa gid na kuya kay ng damo gid ko natun an sa pag

125. budget sa kwarta, sa pag paano ko sya eh ilistahon kung paano gid bala ng

126. pasikotsikot bala haw. Daw hala amo nalang alang na bilin na kwarta bala haw,

127. so dapat listahon ko na tanan nga gin pang kuha namon mga expenses namon,

128. amo pagid na ang ano sa akon pagiging treasurer.

129. Interviewer: Diba subong na pandemic is kumbaga damo gid ta sang problema

130. diba? Ma consider mo ba nga ang inyo nga budget may ara kamo sang

131. pagkukunan or may ara kamo sang source of income subong nga, to conduct

132. your activities kay diba ikaw ang treasurer.

133. Interviewee: Ng satong December kuy, ng halin satong halin sang first namon

134. nga ano wala kami sang kwarta sa SSG gid. So satong december nag conduct

135. kami sang caroling for a cost amo to ang naging fund namon sa kwarta para sa

136. SSG, then tung kwarta namon gin gamin namon para sa pag donate patas

137. satong sa bagyo bala haw na amo to gin gamit namon, then ang iban nga

138. nhabilin sato gin pang donate man namon sa iban sa pag outreach program, sa

139. pag ano sa program namon.

140. Interviewer: With regard sa communication diba isa ka factor na sa

141. communication, diba indi kamo mag kita-kita permi. So, ma consider mo ba ang

142. communication nyo maka communicate kamo effectively during this time?

143. Interviewee: Uhhh, oo kuya kay ng ano man abi siguro depende gid sa

144. personality sa mga officers dyapun kay subong abi ang mga officer mahambal

145. ko nga mahilig gid sila nga mag ano bala haw? Nga nd gid sila mahuya mag

146. Communicate.

147. Interviewer: Okay, last question nalang ni. Ahemmm, Para sa imo paano ang

148. student leadership maka bulig sa imo not now but in the near future?

149. Interviewee: Ang student leadership abi makabulig gid sya sa pag boost sang

150. self confidence sa imo responsibility as officer kag biskan diin ka man kuya or
151. maging ano ka naman, then mahimo mo na sya nga lifestyle mo nga mag ano
152. sa imo nga time management.
153. Interviewer: So diri na natapos ang aton interview gha, Thank you gid.

APPENDIX F

REQUEST LETTER TO THE VALIDATOR

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 221 - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

January 28, 2022

Dear _____,

The undersigned would like to request your approval to be one of the evaluators in the research study in titled **“LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTIES: A NARRATIVE OF STUDENT LEADERS EXPERIENCES IN FACING THE NEW NORMAL”** as a requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English. Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the instrument rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the actual printout of the questionnaire guide and research objectives. Your comments and suggestion will be a great help in the realization of this study.

Looking forward for your favorable response on this request. Thank you and God Bless.

Sincerely;

ROGENT I. LAUDE
Researcher

Noted by;

ALBERT P. BALONGOY, PhD
Research Adviser

APPENDIX G

VALIDATION SHEETS FOR INTERVIEW GUIDE

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
 Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
 Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

For the Evaluator. Please check the appropriate box for your rating.

Point Equivalent:

- 5 - Excellent
- 4 - Very Good
- 3 - Good
- 2 - Fair
- 1 - Poor

Criteria	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Direction and items. The vocabulary level, language structure and conceptual level of respondents. The test directions and items are written in a clear and understanding manner.					
2. Presentation / Organization of items. The items are presented and organized in logical manner.					
3. Suitability of items. The manner items appropriately represent the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perceptions and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.					
4. Adequateness of items Per Category. The items represent the coverage of the research adequately. The number of questions per area is repetitive enough of all the questions needed for the research.					
5. Attainment of the Purpose. The instrument as a whole fulfills the objectives of which was constructed.					
6. Each item question requires only specific answer or measures only behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire suggest bias of the researchers.					
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating System. Scale adapted is appropriate for the items.					

 Name and Signature of Evaluator

APPENDIX H

STUDENT LEADER ADVISER CONSENT FORM

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES – MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling – Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 22/ - 2880

COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

STUDENT LEADER ADVISER CONSENT FORM

I confirm that I am _____ the student leader adviser
of _____.

I hereby give my agreement for my advisee to participate in Rogan I. Laude's research study which is entitled " **LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTIES: A NARRATIVE OF STUDENT LEADERS EXPERIENCES IN FACING THE NEW NORMAL** ". I've included contact information below. I certify that all information is true, and that I am competent to grant my students permission to participate in the study.

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Contact Details

Name of the Participant: _____

Address: _____

Adviser's Mobile Phone no.

Emergency mobile phone no. (1) _____

APPENDIX I

PARENTS CONSENT FORM

RAMON MAGSAYSAY MEMORIAL COLLEGES-MARBEL, INC.
Purok Waling-Waling, Arellano Street, Koronadal City, South Cotabato
Tel. No.: (083) 228-2880
COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

PARENTS CONSENT FORM

I confirm that I am _____ the parent of
_____.

I hereby give my agreement for my son/daughter _____ to participate in Rogen I. Laude's research study which is entitled " **WHEN TIME GETS ROUGH: UNDERSTANDING THE LEADERSHIP DIFFICULTY EXPERIENCES OF STUDENT LEADERS IN THE NEW NORMAL** ". I've included contact information below. I certify that all information is true, and that I am competent to grant my child permission to participate in the study.

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Contact Details

Name of the Participant: _____

Address: _____

Parent's Mobile Phone no.

Emergency mobile phone no. (1) _____

APPENDIX J

PLAGIARISM CHECKER RESULT

 Report: Chapter 1-3 (2)

Chapter 1-3 (2)

by blessed

General metrics

40,997 characters	5,989 words	317 sentences	23 min 57 sec reading time	46 min 4 sec speaking time
----------------------	----------------	------------------	-------------------------------	-------------------------------

Score

92

This text scores better than 92% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

157 Issues left	8 Critical	149 Advanced
--------------------	---------------	-----------------

Plagiarism

6 %

17 sources

6% of your text matches 17 sources on the web or in archives of academic publications

Report was generated on Saturday, Feb 4, 2023, 03:05 PM Page 1 of 42

 Report: Chapter 4-5 (Edited)

Chapter 4-5 (Edited)

by blessed

General metrics

55,652 characters	8,926 words	408 sentences	35 min 42 sec reading time	1 hr 8 min speaking time
----------------------	----------------	------------------	-------------------------------	-----------------------------

Score

95

This text scores better than 95% of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

233 Issues left	49 Critical	184 Advanced
--------------------	----------------	-----------------

Plagiarism

1 %

4 sources

1% of your text matches 4 sources on the web or in archives of academic publications

Report was generated on Saturday, Feb 11, 2023, 09:47 AM Page 1 of 52